

Deliverable No. 1.4

DiscardLess

Strategies for the gradual elimination of discards in European fisheries

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Changes in selectivity, fish stocks and sensitive components over the course of the project, and impact of the landing obligation on ecological knowledge and scientific advice

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Common Fisheries Policy of the European Union was reformed in 2013 to improve the conservation of marine biological resources and the viability of the fishing sector and reduce unsustainable fishing practices (European Union 2013). One of the cornerstones of the reform is Article 15 (termed the Landing Obligation, LO), stipulating the obligation to bring to land all catches of quota- or size-regulated species with the overall aim to gradually eliminate discards.

The shift of focus from landed catches to all catches (i.e. including discards) in the current CFP was expected to have a number of wide-ranging implications both on the ecosystem and on the scientific knowledge and the ways the scientific community is providing advice on fishing opportunities. Changes in the ecosystem were expected in relation to improved selectivity and reduced discards, while changes in the scientific knowledge were expected in relation to i) changes in the collection of discards data, with the additional need for collecting new types of data such as landed discards (BMS, Below Minimum Size landings) and legal discards from de minimis exemptions, and ii) improved knowledge on discards survival and its integration in the scientific advice.

The first aspect (describing the observed changes in the ecosystem) was the first objective of this Deliverable when initially planned in the project. However, a key outcome of the analyses reported here on the implementation period between 2015 and 2018 is that little has changed yet with regards to discards reduction and selectivity improvements, so the actual ecological effects of the landing obligation on the fish stocks and sensitive components of the ecosystem have been limited so far. Most of the changes have been political, but their impacts in terms of discards reduction are not visible yet. Rather, as documented in the section 3, TACs have been adjusted upwards to facilitate the implementation of the LO. Without corresponding discards reduction, this may well lead to counterproductive increases in fishing mortality.

Therefore, considering the limited extent of the ecological changes actually observed, it was decided to expand the scope of this deliverable to the second aspect (section 2), and to also document the impacts of the landing obligation on the scientists, describing how the policy change has impacted the processes of data collection and scientific advice from e.g. ICES and STECF. The title of the deliverable was expanded accordingly.

For each regional case study, this deliverable provides in section 4 an overview of the trends in the main stocks affected by the landing obligation, summarising the published data on discard quantities and trends in biomass and fishing mortality. Secondly, an effort was made to collect information on some of the initiatives for discard reduction being implemented by various Member States, not only those developed in the frame of DiscardLess but also those developed in other fora, and in particular through dedicated fisheries-science partnerships. The only stocks where some changes have been observed over the 2015-2018 period would be the North Sea and west of Scotland haddock, and to a lesser extent North Sea cod and Saithe (in the west of Scotland only) for which discard volumes have decreased.

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1 Introduction

The Common Fisheries Policy of the European Union was reformed in 2013 to improve the conservation of marine biological resources and the viability of the fishing sector and reduce unsustainable fishing practices (European Union 2013). One of the cornerstones of the reform is Article 15 (termed the Landing Obligation, LO), stipulating the obligation to bring to land all catches of quota- or size-regulated species with the overall aim to gradually eliminate discards.

Four years into the process, this document aims at summarising what has changed in our perception of European commercial fish stocks, both in the data and methods used and in the results obtained.

“Achieving MSY” means achieving a level of fishing mortality at F_{MSY} . The fishing mortality accounts for all catches, regardless whether these catches are landed or discarded. In this context, the LO was seen to have a role in improving catch knowledge, since all discards would be landed and thus one would have access to the entire catch profile. The consequent shift of focus from landed catches to all catches (i.e. including discards) has had a number of wide-ranging implications on the scientific ecological knowledge and on the ways the scientific community is providing advice on fishing opportunities, which are detailed in section 2.

On the management side, TACs have been adjusted to facilitate the implementation of the LO, although overall, discarding practices have little changed in Europe to date. This may well lead to counterproductive increases in fishing mortality, as argued in section 3.

The final section summarises the situation in the DiscardLess case studies, providing updated discard plans and listing potential changes in data collection, stock perception or in the broader marine ecosystems.

2 Effects of the landing obligation on scientific documentation, evaluations, data collection and the provision of scientific advice

Beyond the ecological effects on the stocks themselves, the landing obligation has had a number of wide-ranging implications on the scientific ecological knowledge and on the ways the scientific community is providing advice on fishing opportunities. These aspects have been described and developed in the Chapter 3 of the Landing Obligation Book:

Rihan D., Uhlmann S.S., Ulrich C., Breen M., Catchpole T. (2019) Requirements for Documentation, Data Collection and Scientific Evaluations. In: Uhlmann S.S., Ulrich C., Kennelly S.J. (eds) The European Landing Obligation. Springer, Cham. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-03308-8_3

Which has been written collaboratively with authorship from both outside and within the DiscardLess consortium. This book chapter is thus reported and summarised in the present deliverable, but is not a product of DiscardLess alone. A few additional information not included in the book chapter have been added here.

According to the Basic Regulation (EU) 1380/2013, the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) recognises that to ensure good governance, decision-making should, among others, be based on the principles of best available scientific advice. Scientific advice comprises the provision of catch advice for setting fishing opportunities, and evaluation and assessment of specific elements of the CFP.

This book chapter describes the new challenges that the Landing Obligation (Article 15) has posed to the two main advisory bodies: ICES (the International Council for the exploration of the Sea) and STECF (the EU Scientific, Economic and Technical Committee for Fisheries).

The main role of ICES has been to change the focus of the advice provided to the EU Commission from landings to catches to take account of the new management approach under the Landing Obligation. In this context, ICES has considered how best to provide information corresponding to wanted (i.e. catches above minimum conservation reference sizes) and unwanted catches (i.e. catches below minimum conservation reference sizes) and also how to estimate catches discarded under exemptions to the Landing Obligation. ICES has also developed advice and methodologies to support experimental work in relation to high survivability exemptions. Additionally, ICES has received specific requests from the Commission to consider the impacts on the removal of TACs (ICES 2017, 2018) and amending specific Regulations (e.g. the sprat box in the North Sea).

STECF performs scientific work directly requested by the EU Commission. The main body of work carried out by STECF with regard to the Landing Obligation has been in assessing the main provisions and flexibilities provided for in Article 15 and the likely impacts of applying such mechanisms. At the time of writing STECF has held ten Expert Working Groups to advise on various aspects of the Landing Obligation (STECF 2013, 2014a, 2014b, 2014c, 2014d, 2015a, 2015b, 2016a, 2017, 2018). STECF (2015c) has also developed a methodology for the calculation of increases in TACs to take account of catches previously discarded (i.e., so-called TAC uplifts). Finally, STECF has reviewed the mandatory annual reports provided by Member States and the Advisory Councils on the implementation of the Landing Obligation (STECF 2016a, 2017, 2018).

2.1 Ecological knowledge on survival and assessment of High Survival Exemptions

Article 15, paragraph 2(b), of the CFP describes an exemption from the Landing Obligation for “*species for which scientific evidence demonstrates high survival rates, taking into account the characteristics of the gear, of the fishing practices and of the ecosystem*”. Clear, defensible, scientific evidence is required to support any proposal for such an exemption for selected species or fisheries. The inclusion of this provision within the CFP has sparked a sudden and uniquely synchronized interest in discard survival assessments and mobilised Member States and fishing industry representative organisations to apply for research projects to generate supporting evidence.

The book chapter summarised the scientific challenges and required protocols for measuring survival, and gathered the main results of the suite of studies recently published. Regarding protocols, ICES has established a dedicated working group for survival studies, starting with workshop on Methods for Estimating Discard Survival (WKMEDS, ICES 2014). This working group has defined protocols and minimum requirements for conducting and analysing survival studies. Most recent developments aim to estimate expected survival on the basis of the vitality of the fish onboard, instead of through full observation status studies that are difficult and expensive.

Regarding the summary of survival studies, the book chapter has collected the results of more than 20 studies performed in Europe since 2013. This has resulted in an extensive table, included in an online supplement of the book chapter (Table 3.3; in Electronic supplementary material, https://static-content.springer.com/esm/chp%3A10.1007%2F978-3-030-03308-8_3/MediaObjects/978-3-030-03308-8_3_MOESM1_ESM.docx).

The evidence submitted by Member States to support requests for a High Survival Exemption has been evaluated by STECF. Assessing the robustness of evidence, and its representativeness across entire fisheries, has proved challenging for STECF. Additionally, defining what “high survival” means has also been challenging. STECF has highlighted that this is a subjective term that involves trade-offs between different management and societal objectives, driven by the management priority for that fishery at that particular time (e.g., improving stock sustainability; improving financial viability; or avoiding waste). However, survivability should be considered in the context of the discard rates in the fishery, highlighting that medium survival rates in high discarding fisheries still lead to high discard mortality rates.

An example is given in Figure 1 (STECF PLEN 18-02). Plots are interpreted by noting that the lower bar in each case shows the discard rate while the upper bar shows the effect of the addition of the estimated survivability. The key observation is the size of the red ‘dead discards’ bar in the upper plot and the percentage of the overall catch from the exempted fishery that this would represent. In the example given, the dead discards with an exemption in place make up around 15% of the total catch for this fleet. In some cases, the percentage of dead discards is small (below 5%), while in others it can be higher, indicating that a significant proportion of the catch is returned to the sea and dies in the exempted fishery (assuming no change in selectivity).

Figure 1 illustration of the share of dead discards vs. survivors depending on discard and survival rates. (Source STECF PLEN 18-02)

2.2 Monitoring unwanted catch and accounting for them in the ICES advice on fishing opportunities

The book chapter by Rihan et al. (2018) explains also the challenges that the LO has posed to ICES in terms of data collection and advice on fishing opportunities.

The first challenge is linked to the emergence of new catch categories for stock assessment. Initially, catch information comprised only landings, but discard estimates by fishing activity (“*metier*”) have been increasingly available through improved sampling programs financed by the EU Data Collection Framework (Council Regulation (EC) No 199/2008). In 2015, the scientific advice therefore included a complete provision for both landings and discards by *métiers* for most commercial stocks.

Since 2015, even the use of the word “discard” has become challenging. It is still considered that even if landed, a part of the catch is still not targeted by fishermen, but they cannot be called discards anymore and are referred to as “unwanted catch”, while landings are now referred to as “wanted catch”. Unwanted catches now consists of several categories:

- **B = BMS Landings.** Landings below minimum conservation reference size, BMS. Relevant for stocks under the landing obligation. The BMS landing will consist of BMS landings and predator damaged fish.
- **D = Discards.** The part of the catch which is thrown overboard into the sea and not registered in the logbook. This is still based on fishery observer estimates and applying to all stocks, both under and outside the landing obligation.
- **R = Logbook Registered Discard.** Relevant for stocks under landing obligation. Logbook registered discard are discards, which are registered in the logbook and are under the exemption rules (e.g. *de minimis*). Damaged fish can be included under this Logbook registered discard.

The sum of (B+D+R) is the “unwanted catch” and corresponds to what was previously recorded as D alone. Thus, there are now many more catch categories strata to quantify, but the categories B and R are usually not sampled directly by the scientific observers. Until now however, the R and B categories have remained negligible, also in 2018 (e.g. **Error! Reference source not found.**).

unwanted catch 2017 (ICES)

Baltic stocks, 2017-2018

Figure 2: Discards estimated from observations (blue) vs discards declared (green) for selected stocks in the Baltic and North Sea, 2017 ICES data (Top). Bottom: ICES data for the Baltic stocks in 2017 and 2018

The second major change in the process relates to the advice itself; i.e. to the maximum tonnage advised by ICES to be in line with the management objective. The target fishing mortality (e.g., F_{msy}) corresponds to the quantity of dead fish to be removed from the population, regardless of whether they are landed or discarded. Previously, the advice was expressed in terms of landings, assuming a given share of discards based on previous years' observations. In theory, the landing obligation would ensure that all catches would be landed, and a single catch advice would suffice. In practice, this poses a number of quantitative challenges, linked to the facts that: i) discarding still takes place and cannot be ignored; and ii) legal provisions (e.g. high survivability, *de minimis* and predator damage fish) in article 15 mean that the landing obligation is only partially applicable, particularly during the transition period 2015-2018 where not all fleets catching the same stocks have been phased-in at the same time, leading to partial uplifts (see below). It has been impossible to formulate single catch advice that would encompass this management

complexity. ICES has therefore chosen to issue advice as a single maximum catch value, where the split between wanted and unwanted shares enters the calculation but does not appear in the headline anymore, leaving it to the Commission to decide the actual level of the TAC.

In conclusion, the scientific information has become more complex to collect, to use and to quality-check, and to explain to clients in a simple and transparent advice.

ICES advice for North Sea sole in 2015² (top) and 2018³ (bottom)

ICES stock advice

Please note: The present advice replaces the advice given for this stock in June 2015.

ICES advises that when the second stage of the EU management plan (Council Regulation No. 676/2007) is applied, catches in 2016 should be no more than 13 031 tonnes. If discard rates do not change from the average (2012–2014), this implies landings of no more than 12 066 tonnes.

ICES advice on fishing opportunities

ICES advises that when the proposed EU multiannual plan (MAP) for the North Sea is applied, catches in 2019 that correspond to the F ranges in the MAP are between 7451 tonnes and 21 644 tonnes. According to the MAP, catches higher than those corresponding to F_{MSY} (12 801 tonnes) can only be taken under conditions specified in the MAP, whilst the entire range is considered precautionary when applying the ICES advice rule.

2.3 TAC uplifts

An added complexity in setting fishing opportunities is the inclusion of a provision within the CFP that allows for TAC adjustments to be made for those stocks under the Landing Obligation, allowing in theory the discards to be landed. The book chapter describes the complex process and challenges for agreeing on the methodology for calculating these uplifts during the transition period 2015-2018.

2.4 Conclusion

It is well documented that the Landing Obligation is challenging for Member States to implement and for the fishing industry to comply with, but it has also created several challenges for science, as carefully described in the book chapter reported here.

The introduction of the Landing Obligation has increased the potential for uncertainty in the science supporting fisheries management in the EU. Both ICES and STECF have consistently highlighted the lack of reporting by vessel operators of fish discarded under exemptions, discards of fish currently not subject to the landing obligation and catches of fish below MCRS, which compromises the quality of stock assessments and the accuracy of catch forecast. If the data situation does not improve and the true quantities being caught as reported do not reflect the actual removals, then this will have a significant impact on the quality of scientific advice and,

² <http://www.ices.dk/sites/pub/Publication%20Reports/Advice/2015/2015/sol-nsea-reopen.pdf>

³ <http://www.ices.dk/sites/pub/Publication%20Reports/Advice/2018/2018/sol.27.4.pdf>

without a precautionary approach in setting fishing opportunities, a key objective of the CFP in achieving MSY may be compromised. This specific issue is dealt in more details in the next section.

3 Potential risk of the Landing Obligation on fishing mortality

Catches by fisheries subject to the phased introduction of the LO should have been brought to shore and landed. To accommodate the predicted increase in landed catch from such fisheries, since 2015 the relevant TACs were adjusted in accordance with the estimated catch that formerly would have been discarded, but disregarding the level of implementation of the LO. As mentioned in the previous section and corresponding book chapter, the methodology used by the European Commission for calculating these TAC adjustments when setting the fishing opportunities has been highly complex following extensive discussions with Member States. However, since the methodology used in each TAC is not publically available, and since each TAC is a specific case due in particular to numerous mismatches between TACs area and stocks' definition⁴, one cannot directly assess if those calculations are correct. One can however, assess the level of the TACs adjustment by comparing the wanted catch advised by ICES with the set TAC without the adjustment, while taking into account each TAC particularity.

In this context, and following Borges (2018) methodology, TACs set between 2015 and 2019 were compared to maximum advised catch levels in order to determine the impact of the LO in TAC level setting. Since 2015, TACs under the LO have been increased around 30% in tonnage to account for the predicted landed discards (Figure 3). Several of these TACs were already set above wanted catch advice before any adjustments were made (Borges, 2018).

Figure 3 – Number of TACs under the Landing Obligation (grey column), number of TACs adjusted to account for predicted landed discards (yellow column) and average increase in tonnes of the TACs adjusted to account for predicted landed discards (% , red dashed line) per year.

DiscardLess has noted (Figure 2 above and in several deliverables) that progress towards achieving the objectives of the LO of reducing unwanted catch and changing fishing practices is still imperceptible at the end of the transition period. The EC has also concluded in 2018 that there

⁴ <https://www.documents.clientearth.org/wp-content/uploads/library/2016-12-02-mismatch-between-tacs-and-ices-advice-ce-en.pdf>

is a general lack of compliance with the LO and illegal and unrecorded discarding is widespread (EC, 2018), while TAC adjustments are part of the overall package of measures to implement the LO but they should nevertheless not jeopardise the F_{MSY} objective or increase fishing mortality (EC, 2017).

As reported above, considering that TACs have been increased by 30% on average to accommodate the predicted increase in landed catch, but that no significant quantities of discards have been landed, there is a risk that there will be a substantial increase in fishing mortality. In addition, if there is limited and/or biased knowledge regarding catches we may not be able to determine how much fishing mortality has actually increased, and ultimately where stocks status and their exploitation are in reality. In its latest CFP monitoring report (STECF, 2019), STECF shows that in spite of significant improvements over the last 15 years, many stocks are still overexploited in the NE Atlantic, and that the rate of progress has slowed in the last few years (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Trends in stock status in the Northeast Atlantic 2003-2017. Two indicators are presented: blue line: the proportion of overexploited stocks ($F > F_{MSY}$) within the sampling frame (64 to 70 stocks fully assessed, depending on year) and orange line: the proportion of stocks outside safe biological limits ($F > F_{pa}$ or $B < B_{pa}$) (out of a total of 46 stocks) (STECF PLEN 19-01).

In conclusion, the primary objective of the landing obligation, which was to help achieve F_{msy} through avoiding over-TAC mortality by reducing discards, does not seem to be met yet, since discarding still occur. If this situation continues, the outcomes might even be counter-productive, with risks of increased rather than decreased fishing mortality.

4 Changes in fish stocks and sensitive components over the course of the project, and initiatives to reduce discards implemented in each case study

The first two sections of this deliverables provided a general overview of the observed impact of the landing obligation on the scientific knowledge, and its potential impact on the state of the stock. This next section provides a more detailed overview for each of the DiscardLess case study, reporting on the trends in the main stocks affected by the landing obligation and summarising the published data on discard quantities and trends in biomass and fishing mortality. Secondly, an effort was made to collect information on some of the initiatives for discard reduction being implemented by various Member States, not only those developed in the frame of DiscardLess but also those developed in other fora, and in particular through dedicated fisheries-science partnerships.

4.1 EU Overview

The CFP provides for the progressive phasing-in of the landing obligation, with full implementation as of the 1 January 2019. The implementation has been gradual over the different regions, as shown in the figure below from the EU Commission (SWD(2018) 329 final).

Figure 5. Percentage of TACs partially or fully subject to the LO by sea basin and year*

* DP: Discard plans; JR: Joint Recommendations

By 2016, the proportion of EU landings value under the landing obligation (LO) was estimated to be 21%. The Member States with the highest proportion of landings (excluding pelagics) under

the landing obligation were Belgium (61%), the Netherlands (43%), Sweden (39%) and Denmark (38%). By 2019, when full implementation is planned with all EU quota species and those with minimum conservation reference size (MCRS) in the Mediterranean subject to the landing obligation, it is estimated that 40% of landed value will be under the landing obligation. The Member States identified in 2016 still show the highest proportion in landings under the landing obligation (Belgium, the Netherlands, Denmark & Sweden) and are joined by France, the UK, Ireland, Greece and Slovenia; all with at least 40% of landings under the landing obligation.

Member States have a legal obligation to report annually on their progresses on the implementation of the landing obligation. The STECF is in charge of collecting and summarising these annual reports, and provides therefore a global overview for all of the EU. In its 2019 report (STECF PLEN 19-01), These reports contain information on the measures undertaken by Member States to reduce discards and implement the LO, and on the key areas of concerns and difficulties.

The STECF highlighted great differences among Member States in terms of completeness of the national landing obligation reports (Table 1), and its main conclusions were as follows:

- The LO reports by MS contain mostly qualitative statements, generally not supported with data. It is impossible to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the actual progress in implementing the landing obligation or the impacts of the landing obligation.
- It is not possible to identify to what extent levels of unwanted catches have been reduced in specific fleets or for specific fish stocks.
- Only a limited amount of measures and initiatives have been reported, There is very little information provided on the outcomes arising from specific actions such as the proportions of vessels utilising new gears or the extent to which de minimis exemptions are actually utilised. Member States are unable to point to significant changes in fishing practices.
- Choke issues are a major concern but only one MS reports this happening;
- The most important weakness is in the low quantitative reporting of catches (including de minimis, high survival discards and <mcrs) to the extent that it is very unclear what is happening at sea and whether the implementation of the landing obligation is leading to the required changes in fishing practices. Without these it is not possible to assess if the objectives of the LO are being achieved.

Based on these observations, the STECF formulated a number of recommendations, calling first of all for the accurate reporting of all catches. Since catches are not being adequately reported, monitoring at sea needs to increase.

4.2 The Celtic Sea case study

4.2.1 Introduction

The case study is focused on the demersal trawl fisheries in the Celtic Sea, principally carried out by British, Irish and French vessels, within an area shown approximately in the Figure 6.

Figure 6: Map of the region covered in the Celtic Sea Case Study.

4.2.1.1 The Irish fisheries

There are six main métiers involved from Ireland:

- GNS VIIbcgjk Dem – Trips carried out within VIIb, VIIc, VIIg, VIIj, or VIIk using gillnets to target demersal species, such as saithe, ling, and pollack; cod; rays; hake and forkbeard.
- OTB VIIgfhNeph – Bottom otter trawl trips using a codend mesh size of between 70 and 119mm, fishing within the VIIf-h area targeting Nephrops. The Nephrops component of landings constitutes at least 40% of total trip landings.

- OTB VIIjNeph – Bottom otter trawl trips using a codend mesh size of between 70 and 119mm, fishing within VIIj targeting Nephrops. The Nephrops component of landings constitutes at least 35% of total trip landings.
- SSC VIIgj Dem – Trips carried out within VIIg or VIIj using Scottish seines of mesh size 70mm or more to target demersal species, primarily haddock and whiting.
- TBB VIIefgh Dem – Trips carried out within the VIIe-h area using beam trawls with mesh sizes between 80mm and 89mm to target demersal species, like ray and flatfish species, and megrim, monkfish, witch and lemon sole.
- OTB VIIfgjk Dem – Bottom otter trawl trips, regardless of codend mesh size, fishing within VIIf, VIIg, VIIj and VIIk targeting demersal species. Target species groups include whitefish, and ray and flatfish species.

The case study focused mainly on the OTB metiers.

4.2.1.2 The french fisheries

There are four main metiers involved from France:

- OT_CRU bottom trawl trips targeting Nephrops in ICES division VIIf, VIIg, VIIh and VIIk. This metier involves both OTB and OTT. The landings of Nephrops by this French fleet have decrease in recent years, the fishing effort being reallocated to whitefish and anglerfish. The discard rate for this metier is around 13-15 % and discards are mainly composed of hake and nephrops (14% and 22.5 % of the discards in 2013 respectively) followed by megrim, anglerfish and small spotted dogfish that account for around 5% of the discard each (Cornou et al. 2015).
- OT_DEF bottom trawl trips targeting whitefish and benthic fish in ICES division VII (excepted VIIId). This metier targets both gadoids in the central Celtic sea including VIIe and benthic species (ray, megrim and anglerfish) in the Celtic sea and Azores. Since 2012, a square mesh panel has been mandatory. The yearly average discard rate is around 20-25 %. It varies across area and season (from 10 to 35%). Due to the large spatial coverage of this fishery discards are highly diverse (more than 100 species). Discards are mainly composed by haddock, whiting, boarfish, small spotted dogfish and Red gurnard (Cornou et al. 2015).
- GIL_DEF/CEPgillnets trips targeting demersal species, cephalopods and crustaceans along the northern coast of Brittany (VIIh and VIIe). This metier includes both GNS and GTR nets and is represented by two vessels category smaller and larger than 15m. Discards rate varied between 15 and 20% in 2012- 2013. Discards are mainly composed by anglerfish, rays and crabs (including spider crabs)(Cornou et al. 2015).
- OT_DEF_VIIe bottom trawl targeting demersal, benthic species and cephalopods in VIIe specifically. In average the vessels' length is lower than the OT_DEF operating in the central Celtic sea. The discard rate is higher than the other OT_DEF metier with a discard rate between 40-80% depending on the quarter (around 60% in average)(Cornou et al. 2015).
- Other metiers operate in the Celtic sea: OT-DWS are bottom trawler targeting deep water species that mainly operate in ICES division VI and VII but with little catches in area VIIc. In recent year a Danish seine metier has appeared in the fishery, but little information is available (Cornou et al. 2015).

4.2.2 Adopted discard plan for the region

Fisheries subject to the landing obligation

a) Fisheries in Union and International waters of ICES subarea VI and division Vb

Fishery	Gear Code	Fishing gear description	Mesh Size	Landing Obligation
Cod (<i>Gadus morhua</i>), Haddock (<i>Melagrammus aeglefinus</i>), Whiting (<i>Merlangius merlangus</i>) Saithe (<i>Pollachius virens</i>)	OTB, SSC, OTT, PTB, SDN, SPR, TBN, TBS, OTM, PTM, TB, SX, SV, OT, PT, TX	Trawls & Seines	All	Where total landings per vessel of all species in 2015 and 2016*consist of more than 5% of the following gadoids: cod, haddock, whiting and saithe combined, the landing obligation shall apply to haddock and by-catch of sole, plaice, and megrims.
Norway lobster (<i>Nephrops Norvegicus</i>)	OTB, SSC, OTT, PTB, SDN, SPR, FPO, TBN, TB, TBS, OTM, PTM, SX, SV, FIX, OT, PT, TX	Trawls, Seines, Pots, Traps & Creels	All	Where the total landings per vessel of all species in 2015 and 2016* consist of more than 5% of Norway lobster, the landing obligation shall apply to Norway lobster and by-catch of haddock, sole, plaice and megrim.
Saithe (<i>Pollachius virens</i>)	OTB, SSC, OTT, PTB, SDN, SPR, TBN, TBS, OTM, PTM, TB, SX, SV, OT, PT, TX	Trawls	≥100 mm	Where the total landings per vessel of all species in 2015 and 2016 consist of more than 50% of saithe, the landing obligation shall apply to saithe.

* Vessels listed as subject to the landing obligation in this fishery **in accordance with Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No. 2015/2438 and in accordance with Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No. 2016/2375** remain on the list despite the change in the reference period **and** continue being subject to the landing obligation in this fishery.

b) Fisheries for hake and fisheries for megrims, with TAC for ICES subareas VI and VII and Union and International waters of ICES division Vb

Fishery	Gear Code	Fishing gear description	Mesh Size	Landing Obligation
Hake (<i>Merluccius merluccius</i>)	OTB, SSC, OTT, PTB, SDN, SPR, TBN, TBS, OTM, PTM, TB, SX, SV, OT, PT, TX	Trawls & Seines	All	Where the total landings per vessel of all species in 2015 and 2016*consist of more than 10% of hake, the landing obligation shall apply to hake.
Hake (<i>Merluccius merluccius</i>)	GNS, GN, GND, GNC, GTN, GTR, GEN	All Gill Nets	All	All catches of hake shall be subject to the landing obligation.
Hake (<i>Merluccius merluccius</i>)	LL, LLS, LLD, LX, LTL, LHP, LHM	All Long lines	All	All catches of hake shall be subject to the landing obligation.

* Vessels listed as subject to the landing obligation in this fishery **in accordance with Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No. 2015/2438 and in accordance with Commission Delegated**

Regulation (EU) No. 2016/2375 remain on the list despite the change in the reference period **and** continue being subject to the landing obligation in this fishery.

c) Fisheries with TAC covering ICES subarea VII for Norway lobster

Fishery	Gear Code	Fishing gear description	Mesh Size	Landing Obligation
Norway lobster (<i>Nephrops norvegicus</i>)	OTB, SSC, OTT, PTB, SDN, SPR, FPO, TBN, TB, TBS, OTM, PTM, SX, SV, FIX, OT, PT, TX	Trawls, Seines, Pots, Traps & Creels	All	Where the total landings per vessel of all species in 2015 and 2016* consist of more than 10% of Norway lobster, the landing obligation shall apply to Norway lobster.

* Vessels listed as subject to the landing obligation in this fishery **in accordance with Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No. 2015/2438 and in accordance with Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No. 2016/2375** remain on the list despite the change in the reference period **and** continue being subject to the landing obligation in this fishery.

d) Fisheries in ICES subarea VII for saithe

Fishery	Gear Code	Fishing gear	Mesh Size	Landing Obligation
Saithe (<i>Pollachius virens</i>)	OTB, SSC, OTT, PTB, SDN, SPR, TBN, TBS, OTM, PTM, TB, SX, SV, OT, PT, TX	Trawls	≥100 mm	Where the total landings per vessel of all species in 2015 and 2016 consist of more than 50% of saithe, the landing obligation shall apply to saithe.

e) Fisheries in ICES division VIIa

Fishery	Gear Code	Fishing gear	Mesh Size	Landing Obligation
Cod (<i>Gadus morhua</i>), Haddock (<i>Melagrammus aeglefinus</i>), Whiting (<i>Merlangius merlangus</i>) and Saithe (<i>Pollachius virens</i>)	OTB, SSC, OTT, PTB, SDN, SPR, TBN, TBS, OTM, PTM, TB, SX, SV, OT, PT, TX	Trawls & Seines	All	Where total landings per vessel of all species in 2015 and 2016* consist of more than 10% of the following gadoids: cod, haddock, whiting and saithe combined, the landing obligation shall apply to haddock.

g) Fisheries in ICES division VIIe for common sole

Fishery	Gear Code	Fishing gear	Mesh Size	Landing Obligation
Common Sole (<i>Solea solea</i>),	TBB	All Beam trawls	All	All catches of common sole shall be subject to the landing obligation.
Common Sole (<i>Solea solea</i>),	GNS, GN, GND, GNC, GTN, GTR, GEN	All Trammel nets & Gill nets	All	All catches of common sole shall be subject to the landing obligation.

* Vessels listed as subject to the landing obligation in this fishery **in accordance with Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No. 2015/2438 and in accordance with Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No. 2016/2375** remain on the list despite the change in the reference period **and** continue being subject to the landing obligation in this fishery.

h) Fisheries in ICES divisions VIId and VIIe for pollack

Fishery	Gear Code	Fishing gear	Mesh Size	Landing Obligation
Pollack (<i>Pollachius pollachius</i>)	GNS, GN, GND, GNC, GTN, GTR, GEN	All Trammel nets & Gill nets	All	All catches of pollack shall be subject to the landing obligation.

i) Fisheries in ICES divisions VIIb, VIIc and VIIf –VIIk

Fishery	Gear Code	Fishing gear	Mesh Size	Landing Obligation
Common Sole (<i>Solea solea</i>),	TBB	All Beam trawls	All	All catches of common sole shall be subject to the landing obligation
Common Sole (<i>Solea solea</i>),	GNS, GN, GND, GNC, GTN, GTR, GEN	All Trammel nets & Gill nets	All	All catches of common sole shall be subject to the landing obligation.

* Vessels listed as subject to the landing obligation in this fishery **in accordance with Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No. 2015/2438 and in accordance with Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No. 2016/2375** remain on the list despite the change in the reference period and continue being subject to the landing obligation in this fishery.

j) Fisheries in ICES divisions VIIb, VIIc, VIIe and VIIf –VIIk

Fishery	Gear Code	Fishing gear	Mesh Size	Landing Obligation
Cod (<i>Gadus morhua</i>), Haddock (<i>Melagrammus aeglefinus</i>), Whiting (<i>Merlangius merlangus</i>) Saithe (<i>Pollachiusvirens</i>)	OTB, SSC, OTT, PTB, SDN, SPR, TBN, TBS, OTM, PTM, TB, SX, SV, OT, PT, TX	Trawls & Seines	All	Where the total landings per vessel of all species in 2015 and 2016*consist of more than 10% of the following gadoids: cod, haddock, whiting and saithe combined, the landing obligation shall apply to whiting.

* Vessels listed as subject to the landing obligation in this fishery **in accordance with Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No. 2015/2438 and in accordance with Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No. 2016/2375** remain on the list despite the change in the reference period and continue being subject to the landing obligation in this fishery.

Proposals by MS (Joint Recommendations) for 2019 have been evaluated by STECF (PLEN 18-02). Details can be found in section 4.3 of that report, and are tabulated there in table 4.3.3.

Exemptions in 2018

Survival exemptions

The survivability exemption provided for in Article 15(4)(b) of Regulation (EU) No 1380/2013 shall apply:

(a) to Norway lobster (*Nephrops norvegicus*) caught in pots, traps or creels (Gear codes (1) FPO and FIX) in ICES subareas VI and VII;

(b) to catches of common sole (*Solea solea*) below the minimum conservation reference size caught with otter trawl gears (Gear codes OTT, OTB, TBS, TBN, TB, PTB, OT, PT, TX) with cod end mesh size of 80-99 mm in ICES division VIId within six nautical miles of the coast and outside identified nursery areas in the fishing operations meeting the following conditions: vessels with the maximum length of 10 m, maximum engine power of 221 kW, when fishing in waters with the

depth of 30 m or less and with limited tow durations of no more than 1:30 hours. Such catches of common sole shall be released immediately.

De minimis exemptions

By way of derogation from Article 15(1) of Regulation (EU) No 1380/2013, the following quantities may be discarded:

- (a) for whiting (*Merlangius merlangus*), up to a maximum of 6 % of the total annual catches of that species by vessels obliged to land whiting and using bottom trawls and seines of less than 100 mm (OTB, SSC, OTT, PTB, SDN, SPR, TBN, TBS, TB, SX, SV, OT, PT and TX) and pelagic trawls (OTM, PTM) to catch whiting in ICES divisions VII d and VII e;
- (b) for whiting (*Merlangius merlangus*), up to a maximum of 6 % of the total annual catches of that species by vessels obliged to land whiting and using bottom trawls and seines of not less than 100 mm (OTB, SSC, OTT, PTB, SDN, SPR, TBN, TBS, TB, SX, SV, OT, PT and TX) and pelagic trawls (OTM, PTM) to catch whiting in ICES divisions VII b-VII j;
- (c) for whiting (*Merlangius merlangus*), up to a maximum of 6 % of the total annual catches of that species by vessels obliged to land whiting and using bottom trawls and seines of less than 100 mm (OTB, SSC, OTT, PTB, SDN, SPR, TBN, TBS, TB, SX, SV, OT, PT and TX) and pelagic trawls (OTM, PTM) to catch whiting in ICES subarea VII, except divisions VII a, VII d and VII e;
- (d) for Norway lobster (*Nephrops norvegicus*), up to a maximum of 6 % of the total annual catches of that species by vessels obliged to land Norway lobster and fishing for Norway lobster in ICES subarea VII;
- (e) for Norway lobster (*Nephrops norvegicus*), up to a maximum of 2 % of the total annual catches of that species by vessels obliged to land Norway lobster and fishing for Norway lobster in ICES subarea VI;
- (f) for common sole (*Solea solea*), up to a maximum of 3 % of the total annual catches of that species by vessels obliged to land common sole and using trammel and gill nets to catch common sole in ICES divisions VII d, VII e, VII f and VII g;
- (g) for common sole (*Solea solea*), up to a maximum of 3 % of the total annual catches of that species by vessels obliged to land common sole and using TBB gear with mesh size of 80-199 mm with increased selectivity, such as a large mesh extension, to catch common sole in ICES divisions VII d, VII e, VII f, VII g and VII h.

Taken from COMMISSION DELEGATED REGULATION (EU) 2018/46 of 20 October 2017 establishing a discard plan for certain demersal and deep sea fisheries in North-Western waters for the year 2018

4.2.3 Methods for reducing discard

Ten new Irish studies on gear based methods for the reduction of discard and bycatch in the context of the LO have been carried out and published since the start of the project (Browne et al, 2018a, and b. Oliver et al, 2017; McHugh et al, 2017a and b, Cosgrove et al 2016 a, b, c and d and Cosgrove et al, 2015). They concern the Nephrops, cod and whiting fisheries and are downloadable at <http://www.bim.ie/our-publications/fisheries/>

A scheme to promote the use of more selective fishing gears in the Irish Nephrops Fishery has also been proposed in Ireland. This will potentially provide management incentives for fishers using

more selective gears evaluated via the above BIM reports. More information is available at: <https://www.agriculture.gov.ie/seafood/seafoodpolicy/forms/nephropschemeformeuseofselectivefishinggears/>

Three french projects on gear based methods for the reduction of discard and bycatch in the context of the LO have been performed since the start of Discardless project : CELSELECT, REDRESSE and REJEMSELECT. These projects involved Producers Organisations, IFREMER and were funded by the French funding body "France Filière Pêche". Main results were reported using factsheets available on the DiscardLess selectivity manual.

During the CELSELECT project, three selective devices were retained for sea trials in the Celtic sea after two participative workshops involving scientists and the fishing industry. 38 fishing trips on commercial conditions were realized along the project. Most of the selective devices were tested under the twin trawl method, with on one side the gear to be tested and on the other, the standard commercial gear. Two dedicated campaigns were also performed to characterize absolute selectivity curves of both standard and selective gears.

A 100 mm square mesh cylinder in the extension and a 100mm T90 extension and codend were tested to reduce discards of demersal species especially haddock and whiting.

Results of experiment conducted with the 100 mm square mesh cylinder in the extension revealed significant effect of the SMC position and dispersive float on size selectivity of haddock, whiting and megrim. The SMC placed at 12.5m from the cod-line was then tested on commercial conditions. The catch comparison analysis evidenced discard reductions with the test gear compared to the standard commercial trawl of 25%, 60 % and 33% for haddock, whiting and megrim respectively.

Results showed that the test trawl with a 100mm T90 extension and codend halved discard weights without significant reduction in landings, except for red mullet and squid. The test trawl eliminates discards of Gadidae, Triglidae, and Caproidae with discard reduction in weight up to 90%. Analysis of the size composition of catches indicated a significant escape of small fish of several target species (e.g. megrim, haddock, rays, monkfish) and non-target species (e.g. boarfish, gurnard) from the test trawl compared to the control trawl. The device was tested in all four quarters of the year to represent the various fishing strategies and métiers that vessels implement. The fishing master appreciated using the test trawl when the target species were monkfish, megrim, rays and large haddock, but would not use it during trips targeting cephalopods or small whiting or hake (gadoids with a thinner cross-section than haddock).

° A semi elliptic flexible grid in the extension was tested to improve selectivity of benthic species such as monkfish, megrim and rays.

Results of the experiments conducted using semi elliptic sorted grid indicate a general reduction of 20% of discards weight without reduction in landings. The catch comparison analysis evidenced discard reduction with the test gear compared to the standard commercial trawl for flatfish such as megrims, scaldfish, gurnards, small spotted dogfish and dragonet .Analysis of the size composition of catches indicated a significant escape of small monkfish between 10-20 cm. The ergonomy and the robustness were significantly improved compared to previous grids. This

flexible grid is cheap and easily adaptable to optimize the reduction of discards and landings (choice of bars spacing). More information are available in Lamothe et al (2017).

The REDRESSE project conducted in the Bay of Biscay was the opportunity for trawl fleets targeting cephalopods, Nephrops and demersal fish to continue testing various selective configurations to reduce their discards levels. The sea trials were carried out onboard of commercial fishing vessels and the experimental tows were sampled by an observer. Most of the selective devices were tested under the twin trawl method, with on one side the gear to be tested and on the other, the standard commercial gear. Other devices were tested with the parallel or alternate haul method. The data obtained were used to describe the catch species composition as well as their length profiles. Discards and escapement rates of both discarded and commercial fractions were also calculated. Among discards reduction and commercial size escapement, these indicators show the pros and cons of each device tested. The results per species and configuration will let the fishermen make these devices their own according to the specificities and species composition of their fisheries. More information are available in Mehault et al (2018).

The main goal of the REJEMCELEC project was to reduce whiting, haddock and pelagic discards for single bottom trawlers fleets targeting whiting, squids, cuttlefish and monkfish within the Western Channel. A specific fleet targeting hake and John Dory in Celtic Sea during summer (around Scilly Island) was also studied in order to reduce discards of small haddock, hake and boarfish. After a review of the state of the art, an analysis of quantitative data and various workshops, five “selectivity cases” were identified. The selective devices were evaluated with regard to three criteria: reduction of unwanted catches (sizes and species), commercial losses and ergonomomy of the device. Two of them gave interesting results considering these three criteria.

The first one was a T90 panel (80 mm), on the top of the baitings and extension, for the whiting and cephalopods bottom trawl metier in the Western Channel. This device selects the whiting near the last size of the commercial category 40 (32 cm) without commercial loss. In addition, a reduction in the catch of undersized haddock, horse mackerel and mackerel were observed. It is worth noting that the fishing boat having performed the trials continues to use this device on commercial trips.

The second is a large 100mm T90 panel on almost all the top of the extension (13m long on the top of the straight part of the trawl) for fleets targeting hake and John Dory in Celtic Sea during summer. This device was tested as an alternative to the mandatory 120 mm square mesh panel (only 3m long in comparison). The extension of the selective surface (x4) and the adjustment of the mesh to the targeted sizes of hake and haddock, allowed to decrease significantly the catches of small fishes and to increase the catches of good-sized individuals. More information are available in Laviolle et al (2018).

4.2.4 Changes in discards volumes and fish stocks

The top 10 Commercial Fish Species Landed (by weight) from 2003-2009 caught by Demersal Gears are shown in table 2.

Table 2: Main commercial fish species caught by demersal gears landed (by weight) from 2003-2009.

Species	Discards	Landings	Total Catch	Discard Rate	Annual Average Discarded
Nephrops	11,194	51,808	63,312	18%	1,599
Haddock	34,532	28,773	63,306	55%	4,933
Whiting	23,246	19,410	42,656	54%	3,321
Megrim	6,230	14,902	21,132	29%	890
Hake	6,521	12,422	18,942	34%	932
Monkfish	2,756	12,276	15,032	18%	394
Cod	1,140	8,848	9,988	11%	163
Plaice	9,912	3,973	13,885	71%	1,416
Saithe	468	2,963	3,430	14%	67
Witch	2,278	2,271	4,549	50%	325
Total	98,277	157,645	255,922	38%	14,040
Annual Average	14,039	22,251	36,560		

The same information for 2011-2017 are shown in Table 3 below. No assessment data are available for Saithe and Witch.

Species	Discards	Landings	Total	Discard rate	Annual Average discards
Hake	67635	648357	715992	9.45%	9662
Monkfish	28700	264149	292849	9.80%	4100
Haddock	54837	78769	133606	41.04%	7834
Megrim	21470	93862	115332	18.62%	3067
Whiting	28776	84605	113381	25.38%	4111
Nephrops	8026	34487	42513	18.88%	1147
Cod	3821	32259	36080	10.59%	546
Plaice	7718	2903	10621	72.67%	1103
Total	220983	1239391	1460374	15.13%	31569
Annual Average	27623	154924	182547		

Table 3: Main commercial fish species caught by demersal gears landed (by weight), data update 2011-2017.

For the Celtic Sea, assessments (ICES Cat 1 stocks) are available for: Cod, haddock, whiting, nephrops, megrim, and hake. Anglerfish (both species) are Cat 3, there is no assessment or advice for saithe, or witch.

For the anglerfish. The status of *Lophius budegassa* is not known, although the stock biomass is believed to be decreasing. Discarding is believed to be over 5%. For *L. piscatorius*, it is believed to be fished below F_{msy} , and the SSB is believed to be above B_{trig} . Discarding is believed to be over 5%.

Cod VIIe-k

Currently fished below F_{pa} , but above F_{MSY} , SSB below B_{pa} and B_{trig}

Average Discard Rate 2014-2016 = 10.3%

Haddock VIIb-k

Currently fished below F_{pa} , but above F_{MSY} , SSB above B_{pa} and B_{trig}

Discard Rate 2014-2016 increasing from 24% in 2014 to 58% in 2016

Northern Hake IV, VI, VII, and IIIa and IIIa,b,d

Currently fished below F_{pa} , and F_{MSY} , SSB above B_{pa} and B_{trig}

Discard Rate 2014-2016 averages around 10%

Megrim VIIb-k, and VIIa, b, d

Currently fished below F_{pa} , and above F_{MSY} , SSB above B_{pa} and B_{trig}

Discard Rate 2014-2016 range from 12-17%

Plaice VII f,g

Currently fished below F_{pa} , and F_{MSY} , SSB above B_{pa} and B_{trig}

Discard Rate 2014-2016 range from 70-75%

Whiting VIIb,c, e-k

Currently fished below F_{pa} , and F_{MSY} , SSB above B_{pa} and B_{trig}

Discard Rate 2014-2016 range from 24-32%

Nephrops FU 19-22

Currently fished below F_{MSY} in all areas, SSB over B_{trig} except in FU20-21 where no reference value is defined.

Discard Rate 2014-2016 range from 23-36%

4.2.5 Changes in sensitive components of the ecosystem (if appropriate)

None known

4.3 The Western Mediterranean case study

4.3.1 Introduction

The Western Mediterranean case study focuses on two contrasting areas in terms of the ecosystem productivity, exploitation pattern, and types and rates of discards: the French and Spanish Gulf of Lions-Catalan coast and the Balearic Archipelago. These areas encompass three different geographical subareas (GSAs), defined by the General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean (GFCM; www.gfcm.org) for the assessment and management of Mediterranean stocks: 1) Balearic Islands (GSA 5); 2) Northern Spain (GSA 6); and 3) Gulf of Lions (GSA 7). The Gulf of Lions is the most productive area in the western Mediterranean owing to the winter upwelling and the discharges of rivers, whereas the Balearic Islands constitute an especially oligotrophic area within the general oligotrophy of the Mediterranean (Estrada, 1996).

Hake and red mullet from the Gulf of Lions are shared stocks exploited by the French and Spanish demersal fishing fleets. The French trawler fleet is the largest both in number of boats and landings (41% and 72%, respectively). The second largest fleet is the French gillnetters (41 and 14% respectively), followed by the Spanish trawlers (11 and 8%, respectively), and the Spanish long-liners (6 and 6%, respectively). In 2016, the French trawl fleet was composed of 62 vessels from 18 to 25 m length, 57 of which are based on the continental coast and the remaining ones in Corsica. This fleet is relatively homogeneous, half of the trawlers of 18-24 m length and the other half of 24-25 m length. In 2008, the total production of the French fleet was about 16000 tons (50% of the small pelagics—anchovy and sardine) and has recently decreased below 10000 tons (<30% of small pelagics). In parallel, the number of trawlers decreased from 134 vessels in 2005 down to 100 units in 2010 and then to 70 vessels in 2014 (58 in the Gulf of Lions); altogether a reduction of 50% of the fleet size in less than 10 years. Such a reduction, favoured by the introduction of a fishing capacity reduction plan in 2011, may be due to different reasons: i) effort reduction measures as a result of management plans (NOR: TRAM1240482A; NOR: TRAM1304962A; NOR: DEVM1619331A) or spatio-temporal closures (NOR: AGRM1804743A, NOR: AGRM1733988A); ii) collapse of small pelagic fish stocks owing to an ecosystem regime shift (Van Beveren et al., 2014, 2016; Brosset et al., 2015); and iii) increase in fuel cost (30-50% of exploitation costs).

Historically, the number of fishing vessels has remained low in the Balearic Islands compared to nearby areas. In 2016, the commercial fleet included 40 trawlers, 226 small-scale vessels, 7 purse-seiners and 3 long-liners. These values are very far from the total number of vessels in GSA 6, for instance, where the fleet has decreased from 810 trawlers in 1998 to the current 550 units. Trawl fishing exploitation in GSA 5 is much lower than in GSA 6 and 7; the density of trawlers around the Balearic Islands is one order of magnitude lower than in adjacent waters (Quetglas et al, 2012). Landings of the bottom trawl fleet have accounted for between 46 and 70% (mean 59%) in volume and between 60 and 69% (mean 64%) in value of the total landings during 2000-2014. Trawl discards from the continental shelf correspond up to 55-70% of the catch in terms of biomass and are composed mainly of red algae and echinoderms in GSA05, whereas they only represent 23-48% and are dominated by fish in GSA 6 (Sánchez *et al.* 2004, Ordines *et al.* 2006).

4.3.2 Adopted discard plan for the region

i) *Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 1392/2014 of 20 October 2014 establishing a discard plan for certain small pelagic fisheries in the Mediterranean Sea.*

This Regulation specifies the details for implementing the landing obligation in the Mediterranean Sea, to all catches of species which are subject to minimum sizes in small pelagic fisheries. The Article 3 sets out the “de minimis” exemption, which specifies the quantities that may be discarded in the different Mediterranean areas (western Mediterranean, northern Adriatic Sea, southern Adriatic and Ionian Sea, Malta Island and South of Sicily). The regulation shall apply from 1 January 2015 until 31 December 2017.

ii) *Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2016/2376 of 13 October 2016 establishing a discard plan for mollusc bivalve Venus spp. in the Italian territorial waters*

This Regulation specifies the details for implementing the landing obligation that shall apply to Venus spp. fisheries in the Italian territorial waters, setting out the minimum conservation reference size of this bivalve species in that area and specifying that member state authorities shall determine the vessels subject to the landing obligation. The regulation shall apply from 1 January 2017 until 31 December 2019.

iii) *Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2017/86 of 20 October 2016 establishing a discard plan for certain demersal fisheries in the Mediterranean Sea*

In the Mediterranean Sea, as of 1 January 2017 the landing obligation will be compulsory for demersal species that define the fisheries and that are subject to a minimum conservation reference size as defined in the "Mediterranean Regulation (Annex III to Regulation (EC) No 1967/2006). The fisheries targeting hake, red mullet, common sole and deep water rose shrimp in certain areas of the Mediterranean Sea are subject to this provision. This regulation shall apply from 1 January 2017 until 31 December 2019. The new plan establishes detailed rules for the implementation of the landing obligation in these fisheries, including different levels of "de minimis" exemptions depending on the area and fishing gear used. Under this exemption, operators can discard a small percentage of unwanted catches, given that the costs of their handling would be disproportionate.

The plan also stipulates a number of survivability exemptions, allowing operators to throw back specimen that have a high chance of surviving (for example sole caught with beam trawls and scallop, carpet clams and venus shells caught with mechanized dredges). The survivability exemptions are delivered for one year, and Member States are to provide additional scientific data in the course of 2017 for possible renewal.

These exceptions were examined by the EU's scientific advisory body, i.e. the Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries (STECF). All the provisions of the discard plan stem from the joint recommendations drawn up by the Member States concerned namely Greece, Spain, France, Croatia, Italy, Cyprus, Malta and Slovenia, after consultation of the Mediterranean Sea Advisory Council.

One year later, several articles of this Delegated Regulation were amended by the Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2018/153 of 23 October 2017.

4.3.3 Methods for reducing discards

Two new initiatives have arisen during the development of DiscardLess project. The first one is the introduction of doors that do not touch the seabed in the bottom trawling, which has been demonstrated as a plausible technical measure to be applied in the trawl fishery of the Balearic Islands (Guijarro et al., 2017). Although this measure does not reduce discards, it is a very efficient measure to reduce the direct physical impact of the bottom trawling. The fishing sector was interested in this measure because it implies a reduction in the fuel consumption with the consequent reduction of the operating costs. In fact, on December 30th 2017 the Autonomous Government of the Balearic Islands (CAIB) published a call for grants for the fishing sector to develop the measure 1.1.2 included in the Spanish operational program of the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund (EMFF) "Limitation of the impact of fishing on the marine environment and adaptation of fisheries to the protection of species. Change of doors". This program will be developed between 2018 and 2020 and will establish grants of up to 35000 € per commercial fishing vessel of the Balearic Islands for the acquisition of "Equipment that limits and, if possible, eliminates the physical and biological effects of fishing activities in the marine ecosystem and seafloor. These equipments must be validated by a recognized scientific entity". These subsidies will be co-financed by EMFF (75%) and the local government (25%).

The second initiative was developed by the skipper of the F/V Nueva Joven Josefina (length 21.0 m, 44 grt, nominal engine power 150 hp), a bottom trawler based on Maó which operates on the traditional fishing grounds off Menorca (Balearic Islands). It consists of the modification of the attachment of the net to the ground-rope and the use of large rock hoppers or bobbins. According to this skipper, this system allows a considerable decrease in the capture of calcareous algae (rhodoliths) and non-commercial mega-benthic invertebrates (e.g. echinoderms, sponges and ascidians), without a reduction of commercial yields. Considering that in shallow waters of the continental shelf these species represent a great proportion of capture (Ordines et al., 2006), this could be a very valuable measure to improve the selectivity of this fishery. However, its implementation will require the development of experimental fishing pilot project/s to scientifically assess and validate the reduction of discards with this measure and its effectiveness for the bottom trawl fishery of the Balearic Islands. One such project was submitted in June 2018 by the Fishermen Association of the Balearic Islands, jointly with the DiscardLess team of the Spanish Institute of Oceanography (IEO) and the University of Cádiz, to the call PLEAMAR 2018 (Biodiversity Foundation of the Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Environment), funded by EMFF.

4.3.4 Changes in data collection

Discard data are collected at sea under Spanish and French on board sampling programmes funded by the Data Collection Framework (EC, 199/2008). For sampling purposes, only the major métiers are considered, which are selected using a ranking system. Only those métiers whose accumulated shares in landings, value and effort are included in the top 90% are selected. For this reason, the métiers sampled can change with the years. The best information on discards comes from the following métiers of the bottom trawl fleet (OTB: Bottom otter trawl): OTB_DEF (demersal species), OTB_MDD (mixed demersal and deep water species) and OTB_DWS (deep water species) for the Balearic Islands, OTB_DEF and OTB_DWS for the Spanish fleet and OTB or OTT (Twin otter trawl)_DEF and OTM_SPF (Pelagic trawl targeting small pelagic species) for the French fleet operating in the Gulf of Lions.

The sampling design is stratified by area (GSA), with port and trip as primary and secondary sampling unit respectively. Information on discards is used as inputs in the main target species stock assessments carried out annually in the framework of the GFCM and the STECF. These stocks are: 1) In the Balearic Islands: *Merluccius merluccius*, *Mullus barbatus*, *Mullus surmuletus*, *Aristeus antennatus*, *Nephrops norvegicus* and *Parapenaeus longirostris*; and 2) In the Gulf of Lions: *M. merluccius* and *M. barbatus*. In the case of the Gulf of Lions, these assessments are carried out using datasets from both the Spanish (IEO) and French (IFREMER) fleets.

The sampling coverage for each métier in both areas is summarized in Table 2. The mean coverage in the Balearic Island is around 0.5% for OTB_DEF and OTB_DWS and 0.75% for OTB_MDD. In the Gulf of Lions, for the Spanish fleet, the coverage is higher, with a mean around 1% for OTB_DEF and around 2% for OTB_DWS. The French fleet coverage included both OTB or OTT_DEF and OTM_SPF (although mostly OTB or OTT_DEF in recent years following the collapse of small pelagic stocks) and was above 1%.

Table 4: Sampling coverage by métier, for the two areas included in the Western Mediterranean case study (Balearic Islands and Gulf of Lions) during 2012-2014.

Area	Metier	Year	Total trips	Sampled trips	Coverage (%)
Balearic Islands	OTB_DEF	2012	3638	17	0.47
		2013	3105	12	0.39
		2014	3528	17	0.48
		2015	4271	13	0.30
		2016	3642	11	0.30
		2017	2834	12	0.42
	OTB_DWS	2012	582	12	2.06
		2013	1032	20	1.94
		2014	888	17	1.91
		2015	334	9	2.69
		2016	623	9	1.44
		2017	350	10	2.86
	OTB_MDD	2012	2039	13	0.64
		2013	1956	12	0.61
		2014	2839	13	0.46
		2015	2109	12	0.57
		2016	2444	11	0.45
		2017	1580	11	0.70
Gulf of Lions Spanish fleet	OTB_DEF	2012	2583	19	0.74
		2013	1296	12	0.93
		2014	1631	17	1.04
		2015	2130	22	1.03
		2016	1827	17	0.93
		2017	2020	23	1.14
	OTB_DWS	2012	559	11	1.97
		2013	501	11	2.20
		2014	655	14	2.14
		2015	693	17	2.45
		2016	565	12	2.12
		2017	392	11	2.81
Gulf of Lions French fleet	OTB_DEF	2011	10159	47	0.46
		2012	5714	70	1.23
	OTB_DEF, OTT_DEF & OTM_SPF	2013	5844	79	1.35
		2014	9928	108	1.09
		2015	10161	118	1.16
		2016	10908	116	1.06
2017	10740	108	1.01		

4.3.5 Changes in discards volumes and fish stocks

Values of total landed and discarded biomass (in tons) of the bottom trawl fleet (BTF) for the main species under the minimum landing size (MLS) by métier during 2012-2017 are shown in Table 3 (Balearic Islands), Table 4 (Gulf of Lions, Spanish fleet) and Table 5 (Gulf of Lions, French fleet).

The 2012-2017 average discard biomass rates for the Balearic Islands are shown in Figure 7. The average percentage of discards is in general lower than 10% for most of the species subjected to the regulation, except for small pelagic species: *T. trachurus* (HOM) and *S. pilchardus* (PIL) in OTB_DEF; and *T. trachurus* (HOM) and *T. mediterraneus* (HMM) in MDD. Small pelagic species are caught as a by-catch of the BTF in this area and their importance is highly variable, both in terms of catches (their catchability shows important oscillations) and in terms of their final destination

(they are landed or discarded depending on different factors, including market interest). This can be seen in Table 1, where their biomass (both landed and discarded) varies significantly among years.

Figure 7: Average percentage of discards, by biomass, for the Balearic Islands (2012-2017) by métier and species. Error bars indicate standard errors. ANE: *Engraulis encrasicolus*; DPS: *Parapenaeus longirostris*; HKE: *Merluccius merluccius*; HMM: *Trachurus mediterraneus*; HOM: *T. trachurus*; MAZ: *Scomber spp*; MUR: *Mullus surmuletus*; MUT: *M. barbatus*; NEP: *Nephrops norvegicus*; PAC: *Pagellus erythrinus*; SBA: *P. acarne*; SBR: *P. bogaraveo*; PIL: *Sardina pilchardus*; RPG: *Pagrus pagrus*; SBG: *Sparus aurata*; SRG: *Diplodus spp*.

The 2012-2017 average discard biomass rates of the Spanish OTB fleet from the Gulf of Lions are shown in Figure 8. The average percentage of discards is in general lower than 10% for most of the species subjected to the regulation, except again for the case of small pelagic species like *E. encrasicolus* (ANE) and *S. pilchardus* (PIL) in OTB_DEF. Similarly of what happens in the Balearic Islands, their importance is highly variable, as it can be seen in Table 3.

Figure 8: Average percentage of discards, by biomass of the Spanish OTB fleet from the Gulf of Lions (2012-2017) by métier and species. Error bars indicate standard errors. ANE: *Engraulis encrasicolus*; DPS: *Parapenaeus longirostris*; HKE: *Merluccius merluccius*; HMM: *Trachurus mediterraneus*; HOM: *T. trachurus*; MAZ: *Scomber spp*; MUR: *Mullus surmuletus*; MUT: *M. barbatus*; NEP: *Nephrops norvegicus*; PAC: *Pagellus erythrinus*; SBA: *P. acarne*; SBR: *P. bogaraveo*; PIL: *Sardina pilchardus*; RPG: *Pagrus pagrus*; SBG: *Sparus aurata*; SRG: *Diplodus spp*.

Based on both the regular DCF sampling on board program and the Galion research project, a larger than usual number of observations were carried out in 2016 and 2017 (636 trips sampled for 21648 fishing trips, hence an exceptional coverage of almost 3%). The 2016-2017 average discard biomass rates of the French trawlers' fleet (mostly using bottom otter trawls OTB and twin otter trawls OTT) from the Gulf of Lions is shown in Figure 9. The average percentage of discards is in general relatively high except for the demersal species subjected to the regulation (here hake and red mullet). Small pelagic species like *E. encrasicolus* (ANE) and *S. pilchardus* (PIL) are not targeted by these métiers which also resulted in high discard rate for these two otherwise regulated species. The data also showed that this discarding behaviour was partly due to market demand as even individuals above minimum landing size were often discarded (from 20% to 100% of discarded volumes depending on species).

Figure 9: Average percentage of observed discards, by biomass of the French OTB-OTT fleet from the Gulf of Lions (2012-2017) by species. Error bars indicate standard deviations. ANE: *Engraulis encrasicolus*; HKE: *Merluccius merluccius*; MUT: *Mullus barbatus*; MUR: *M. surmuletus*; SBA: *Pagellus acarne*; SBR: *P. bogaraveo*; PAC: *P. erythrinus*; DPS: *Parapenaeus longirostris*; PIL: *Sardina pilchardus*; MAS: *Scomber japonicus*; MAC: *Scomber scomber*; SOL: *Solea solea*; HMM: *Trachurus mediterraneus*; HOM: *T. trachurus*

Table 5: Landed and discarded biomass by métier from the Balearic Islands during 2012-2017.

Métier	Species	Landings (t)						Discards (t)					
		2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
OTB_DEF	ANE	0.01						0.00					
	DPS	3.56	5.77	4.70	5.46	6.88	36.72	0.41	0.32	0.01	0.00	1.98	0.60
	HKE	43.98	89.79	85.40	67.05	49.94	44.47	6.44	12.65	4.87	0.59	2.35	0.89
	HMM	47.86	38.08	1.00	0.35	0.73	0.18	9.24	0.19	0.77	0.32	0.21	0.00
	HOM	23.64	18.79	82.19	101.54	79.80	75.23	3.80	17.65	15.26	30.61	205.87	180.36
	MUR	69.93	57.55	64.97	65.85	75.77	81.25	5.54	0.08	2.72	0.14	2.26	1.48
	MUT	14.93	12.30	1.13	1.28	10.23	13.27	0.37	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.09	0.08
	NEP	13.04	11.26	19.96	37.83	14.76	25.37	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.01
	PAC	14.39	11.43	8.67	10.08	10.31	10.84	0.62	0.68	0.11	0.00	0.02	0.00
	PIL	0.07	0.22	0.05	0.10			0.00	19.30	2.38	0.00		
	RPG	0.78	0.84	0.88	0.85	0.73	0.99	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	SBA	8.81	7.02	8.23	3.71	8.02	8.88	0.62	0.00	0.02	0.05	0.00	0.00
	SRG	12.03	3.91	2.52	3.64	2.86	1.71	0.56	0.00	0.09	0.00	0.23	0.00
OTB_DWS	HKE	9.63	9.70	15.69	15.72	5.58	4.12	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	NEP	8.42	3.58	4.65	14.03	5.77	4.98	1.19	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01
	SBA	0.04						0.00					
OTB_MDD	DPS	0.61	0.43	0.89	2.12	2.21	31.31	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00
	HKE	7.58	9.22	17.17	18.82	11.12	23.36	0.06	0.40	0.69	0.02	0.62	0.00
	HMM	9.75	7.23	0.29	2.41	3.65	2.15	4.53	0.92	0.04	2.51	0.00	0.00
	HOM	4.82	3.57	23.41	19.59	17.21	25.35	0.03	0.82	11.52	8.47	13.70	6.52
	MUR	15.58	12.13	14.29	15.27	17.12	18.90	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00
	MUT	3.33	2.60	0.25				0.00	0.00	0.00			
	NEP	8.04	3.98	6.19	21.01	7.80	27.47	0.87	0.00	0.03	0.74	0.00	0.00
	PAC	3.13	2.26	1.54	1.87	1.40	1.75	0.00	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	SBA	1.92	1.39	1.47	0.75	1.69	1.57	0.00	0.04	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.38
	SRG	1.33	1.06	0.79	1.24	0.71	0.34	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

ANE: *Engraulis encrasicolus*; DPS: *Parapenaeus longirostris*; HKE: *Merluccius merluccius*; HMM: *Trachurus mediterraneus*; HOM: *Trachurus trachurus*; MUR: *Mullus surmuletus*; MUT: *Mullus barbatus*; NEP: *Nephrops norvegicus*; PAC: *Pagellus erythrinus*; PIL: *Sardina pilchardus*; RPG: *Pagrus pagrus*; SBA: *Pagellus acarne*; SBG: *Sparus aurata*; SBR: *Pagellus bogaraveo*; SRG: *Diplodus* spp.

Table 6: Landed and discarded biomass by year and métier of the Spanish OTB fleet from the Gulf of Lions during 2012-2017.

Métier	Species	Landings (t)						Discards (t)					
		2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
OTB_DEF	ANE	3.97	2.00	1.98	9.34	0.38	0.07	45.00	1.40	3.53	0.00	0.21	0.01
	DPS	1.70	2.02	2.76	4.73	19.73	30.72	0.30	0.29	0.03	0.03	0.10	0.23
	HKE	154.40	187.57	184.66	107.59	98.08	75.82	1.16	0.13	2.29	1.32	1.19	0.10
	HMM	2.83	2.21	4.90	0.43	12.99		0.00	0.00	0.00			
	HOM	53.10	41.39	63.76	45.59	38.70	44.47	10.08	2.81	0.20	5.45	3.45	0.00
	MAZ	27.25	36.67	40.76	16.8	27.68	13.22	8.02	0.21	0.13	0.00	0.00	0.00
	MUR	0.20	0.25	9.49	16.13	4.77	9.05	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	MUT	28.82	36.89	40.45	32.43	42.38	30.72	0.17	0.01	0.05	0.41	0.83	0.00
	NEP	23.54	18.17	18.94	16.97	15.31	17.76	1.01	0.01	0.06	0.25	0.01	0.04
	PAC	8.54	7.08	7.18	5.02	4.27	0.13	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	PIL	1.64	0.66	0.69	0.19	0.18	0.09	1.69	0.00	0.23	0.03	0.00	0.00
	SBA	15.49	8.01	9.74	8.91	1.76	3.53	0.00	0.00	0.38	0.11	2.03	0.00
	SBG	0.88	2.13	0.33	1.23	1.53	0.22	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	SBR	2.08	1.88	3.28	1.96	5.45	4.55	0.00	0.04	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00
	SRG	2.14	1.92	0.87	1.87	0.87	0.89	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
OTB_DWS	HKE	3.52	6.81	8.38	5.63	3.27	3.47	0.00	0.16	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00
	MAZ		0.02						0.00				
	NEP	1.33	1.73	1.13	0.79	0.71	0.17	0.04	0.33	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00
	SBR	0.11	0.09		0.15			0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00		

ANE: *Engraulis encrasicolus*; DPS: *Parapenaeus longirostris*; HKE: *Merluccius merluccius*; HMM: *Trachurus mediterraneus*; HOM: *Trachurus trachurus*; MAZ: *Scomber spp*; MUR: *Mullus surmuletus*; MUT: *Mullus barbatus*; NEP: *Nephrops norvegicus*; PAC: *Pagellus erythrinus*; PIL: *Sardina pilchardus*; RPG: *Pagrus pagrus*; SBA: *Pagellus acarne*; SBG: *Sparus aurata*; SBR: *Pagellus bogaraveo*; SRG: *Diplodus spp*.

Table 7: Landed and discarded biomass per year and métier of the French OT fleet from the Gulf of Lions during 2012-2017.

Only species with yearly landings above 30t are shown.

Métiers	SPECIES	Landings (t)						Discards (t)					
		2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
OTB_DEF, OTB_CEP, OTB_DEMSP, OTB_SPF	HKE	758.78	1291.52	1264.54	765.72	1170.64	351.41	9.20	45.89	44.47	21.04	19.57	4.67
	OCC		416.06	333.86	327.74	1479.79	473.25						
	MAZ					909.66	249.34						
	POD					623.69	204.53						
	HOM					612.02	173.02						
	ANK	178.62	321.17	339.95	355.92	553.24	158.87	26.67					2.33
	GUR					427.68	163.86						
	MUT	135.32	210.46	254.24	262.68	488.78	87.64	14.78	16.25	9.49	34.51	1.30	2.85
	SQR					320.22	87.17						
	MUL					213.13	76.49						
	SQM					229.05	45.28						
	MTS					187.71	59.54						
	ANE				305.56	51.04	1.95						34.53
	BOG					176.53	52.75						
	SBG	76.33	66.21	134.48	154.27	230.86	18.06						
	PAC					175.53	33.67						
	SBA					164.21	17.81						
	RPW					110.61	50.84						
	MAS			69.33	60.95	96.92	76.56						
	CTC					107.48	19.77						
	SOL	65.41	67.20	53.27	51.39	90.65	29.87						
	DPS					68.73	16.87						
	MUR	21.03	45.13	36.21	61.65	58.40	19.29				34.51	2.34	
	MON	11.59	82.39	64.58	35.49	32.58	12.92						
	GUG					41.09	15.52						
	SYC			30.62	31.04	36.27	5.86						
SRG					35.26	5.74							
RSE					31.07	8.84							

Métiers	SPECIES	Landings (t)						Discards (t)					
		2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
OTT_DEF, OTT_DEMSP, OTT_SPF	POD					292.73	183.94						
	OCC			39.78	22.36	451.20	278.75						
	HKE			104.72	40.13	377.67	172.43			3.68	0.99	6.49	3.17
	HOM					201.66	123.45						
	ANK			65.87	35.25	265.16	186.84						4.81
	MAZ					183.67	92.89						
	MUT			25.03	15.37	197.80	69.89			0.94	2.65	0.03	3.11
	SQR					114.77	37.79						
	SQM					97.80	36.17						
	MTS					76.83	33.38						
	MAS					28.27	40.77						
GUR					31.62	37.01							
OTM_DEF, OTM_DEMSP, OTM_SPF	ANE	1537.49	2434.13	2232.79	793.30	1225.69	595.10						
	PIL	46.02	406.17	82.51	53.37	155.51	13.91			320.00			
	HKE			22.25	14.44	18.34	4.08			0.78	0.28	0.02	
	SBG			11.02	0.82	37.66	6.20						

OTB: Bottom otter trawl, OTT: Twin otter trawl, OTM: mid water trawl, DEF: Demersal Fish, DEMSP: Demersal species, CEP: Cephalopod, SPF: Small pelagic fish, HKE: *Merluccius merluccius*; OCC : *Octopus vulgaris*; MAZ: *Scomber spp*; POD: *Trisopterus minutus*; HOM: *Trachurus trachurus*; ANK: *Lophius budegassa*; GUR: *Aspitrigla cuculus*; MUT: *Mullus barbatus*; SQR: *Loligo vulgaris*; MUL: *Mugilidae*; SQM: *Illex coindetii*; MTS: *Squilla mantis*; ANE: *Engraulis encrasicolus*; BOG: *Boops boops*; SBG: *Sparus aurata*; PAC: *Pagellus erythrinus*; SBA: *Pagellus acarne*; RPW: *Rapana venosa*; MAS: *Scomber japonicus*; CTC: *Sepia officinalis*; SOL: *Solea solea*; DPS: *Parapenaeus longirostris*; MUR: *Mullus surmuletus*; MON: *Lophius piscatorius*; GUG: *Eutrigla gurnardus*; SYC: *Scyliorhinus canicula*; SRG: *Diplodus spp.*; RSE: *Scorpaena scrofa*; PIL: *Sardina pilchardus*

4.4 Bay of Biscay case study

4.4.1 Introduction

The Bay of Biscay (Figure 10) is a highly productive system. It creates the perfect conditions for multispecies trawling fleets to make use of this productivity. In particular there is a trawl fleet based in the ports of Ondarroa (Basque Country, Spain) operating in this area and targeting more than 48 different species and landing and selling always back in Ondarroa.

Figure 10. Case study area: Bay of Biscay

The operation of this fleet can be divided into métiers. These métiers are based on the target assemblage landed by trip, as stipulated in the Commission Decision 2008/949/EC⁵ Appendix IV footnote (b). However, this Commission decision only considered general and non-specific assemblage of species (crustaceans, cephalopods, demersal fish ...), which are not detailed enough to define the different fishing tactics followed by this fleet. Based on direct interviews with skippers, three different “group of target species” were identified; the percentage of each group within the landing is later used to allocate trips into define métiers.

A first métier, pair trawlers (PTB hereafter), use a very high vertical opening bottom trawl to target hake. The activity is constant along the year, with a slight effort reduction during summer period. Total landings reach 2293 tons in 2013, and hake landings (the main target species) 1682 tones.

A second métier, bottom otter trawlers targeting demersal species (OTD hereafter), has a constant activity throughout the year, with slight reduction in effort during summer period. Total landings reach 2836 tons in 2013. Hake (*Merluccius merluccius*), anglerfishes (*Lophius piscatorius* and *Lophius budegassa*) and megrims (*Lepidorhombus whiffiagonis*) are the main landed species, but there are more than 65 other landed species (pouts, dogfish, triglids...).

⁵ COMMISSION DECISION of 6 November 2008 adopting a multiannual Community programme pursuant to Council Regulation (EC) No 199/2008 establishing a Community framework for the collection, management and use of data in the fisheries sector and support for scientific advice regarding the common fisheries policy

The third métier, bottom otter trawlers targeting mixed species (OTM hereafter) concentrates its activity during winter seasons. Total landings reached 655 tons in 2013. Squids, cuttlefish, and mullets are the main target species in this métier.

PTB is mainly landing hake. Total discards are around 15 % of the total catch. Hake individuals under minimum landing size (MLS hereafter) and pelagic species (horse mackerel, and mackerel) are the main component of the discarded catch fraction. There are both market and regulation reasons for discarding within this métier. Hake (MLS) and mackerel (quota exhaustion) are discarded due to legal reasons. Market reasons lie behind horse mackerel discards.

OTD mainly lands hake, anglerfish and megrim, but there are more than 65 other landed species (pouts, dogfish, triglids...). Total discards are around 60-65 % of the total catch. Hake individuals under MLS and pelagic species such as horse mackerel (*Trachurus trachurus*) and mackerel (*Scomber scombrus*) are the main component of the discarded catch fraction.

OTM mainly lands squids, cuttlefish, and mullets are the main target species in this métier. However, this is a very mixed métier including many other species (pout, seabass, hake...), most of them not subject to any total allowable catch (TAC) or MLS.

4.4.2 Adopted discard plan for the region

The obligation of landing all the Unwanted Unregulated Catches in the Bay of Biscay was implemented first for the pelagic quota species (in 2015) which are targeted mainly by pelagic trawlers, purse seines and lines (see Table 8). In 2016, the obligation was extended to some demersal quota species, which are mainly targeted by The discard plan is defined by the following Commission Delegated Regulations (CDR): CDR (EU) No 1394/2014⁶ and the CDR (EU) 2018/188⁷ for pelagic species and the CDR (EU) 2015/2439⁸, the CDR (EU) 2016/2374⁹, CDR (EU) 2017/2167¹⁰ and the CDR (EU) 2018/44¹¹ for demersal species.

Following these regulations and focusing the list of species that are affected by the LO and the exemptions that are in place is provided in Table 8 and Table 9 for pelagic and demersal species respectively.

⁶ COMMISSION DELEGATED REGULATION (EU) No 1394/2014 of 20 October 2014 establishing a discard plan for certain pelagic fisheries in south-western waters

⁷ COMMISSION DELEGATED REGULATION (EU) 2018/188 of 21 November 2017 amending Delegated Regulation (EU) No 1394/2014 establishing a discard plan for certain pelagic fisheries in South-Western waters

⁸ COMMISSION DELEGATED REGULATION (EU) 2015/2439 of 12 October 2015 establishing a discard plan for certain demersal fisheries in south-western waters

⁹ COMMISSION DELEGATED REGULATION (EU) 2016/2374 of 12 October 2016 establishing a discard plan for certain demersal fisheries in South-Western waters

¹⁰ COMMISSION DELEGATED REGULATION (EU) 2017/2167 of 5 July 2017 amending Delegated Regulation (EU) 2016/2374 establishing a discard plan for certain demersal fisheries in South-Western waters

¹¹ COMMISSION DELEGATED REGULATION (EU) 2018/44 of 20 October 2017 amending Delegated Regulation (EU) 2016/2374 establishing a discard plan for certain demersal fisheries in South-Western waters

Table 8: Pelagic fisheries affected by the LO and exemptions in place in the study area.

Fishing gear	Quota species targeted	Exemption in place
Pelagic pair- and otter- trawls (midwater)	Horse mackerel	<i>De minimis</i> (4 % in 2018, 2019 and 2020)
	Mackerel	<i>De minimis</i> (4 % in 2018, 2019 and 2020)
	Anchovy	<i>De minimis</i> (4 % in 2018, 2019 and 2020)
	Albacore tuna	<i>De minimis</i> (6 % in 2018, and 5 % in 2019 and 2020)
	Blue whiting	<i>De minimis</i> (6 % in 2018, and 5 % in 2019 and 2020)
Purse seines	Horse mackerel	<i>De minimis</i> (4 % in 2018, 2019 and 2020) Survivability when slipping in purse seines
	Mackerel	<i>De minimis</i> (4 % in 2018, 2019 and 2020)
	Jack Mackerel	<i>De minimis</i> (4 % in 2018, 2019 and 2020)
	Anchovy	<i>De minimis</i> (1 % in 2018, 2019 and 2020)
Handlines and pole lines, bait boats, trolling lines	Albacore tuna	No exemption
	Mackerel	No exemption

Table 9: Demersal fisheries affected by the LO and exemptions in place in the study area.

Fishing gear	Quota species targeted	Exemption in place
Pair- and bottom otter- trawls	Sole	<i>De minimis</i> (5%)
	Hake	<i>De minimis</i> (7% in 2016 and 2017, and 6 % in 2018)
	<i>Nephrops</i>	High survivability
Trammel and Gill nets	Sole	<i>De minimis</i> (3%)
	Hake	No exemption
	Anglerfish	No exemption
Long lines	Hake	No exemption
	Black scabbardfish	Low-frequency occurrence

4.4.3 Methods for reducing discard

Interviews with fishermen showed their interest in minimizing the unwanted catches as a consequence of the implementation of the LO. These fishermen assured that there were making real efforts to avoid fishing in areas with big amounts of small pelagics, though there is no scientific evidence yet.

The exact mechanism to avoid the small pelagics is based on fishing on deeper grounds (close to the end of the French continental shelf) where the probability of catching these small pelagics (specially mackerel) is reduced.

Current studies more specifically centered on selectivity in the Bay of Biscay waters shows that it is difficult to improve the selectivity (i.e. increase hake escapement) without too much commercial losses for the fishing firms. However, selectivity programs are still running with the aim, in the mid-term, to keep trying new and existing selectivity devices and solutions adapted to the specificities of Biscay Bay waters trawl fisheries;

Selectivity trials for hake catches were experimented on board pair trawls and otter trawlers targeting hake in ICES area 8abd. Promising results were obtained for pair trawls in relation to different configurations of Square Mesh Panel (SMP) for reduction of hake smaller than 27 cm (MRCS).

During November 2016, different technical alternatives were trialled to increase the contacts between hake and the SMP. The strategy with the pair trawl (average towing speed 2 knots) was to change the position of the SMP from the upper panel of the trawl to the lower panel, to account for the observed behaviour of hake, staying more frequently in the lower part of the trawl. The SMP as well as the codend were covered to obtain in each fishing operation a complete view of

the effect of the position of the SMP on hake. In addition, an underwater camera was set in front of the SMP to observe the behaviour of fish in relation with SMP. No results have been achieved with the tested configurations. No fish was present in the cover of the SMP and the catch recorded in the codend and cover of the codend was very low. The conclusion was that the SMP cover was affecting the behaviour of the extension piece of the trawl and avoiding the entrance of fish to the haft part of the trawl. In consequence, no concluding results were derived from these experiments in relation with selectivity improvement. Therefore, no definitive conclusions can be taken and the technical mechanism has not been implemented by the fleet.

For the specific case of the Baka trawlers, hake selectivity trials in Div. 8abd showed that hake catch did not change even when selective devices were used. In conclusion, in relation to the Baka Otter trawls, considering the behaviour observed in the net, the combination of guiding ropes, lights and the SMP placed in the upper plan of the trawl (all these tested in the period 2016-2018), does not seem to lead to an increase in the escapement rates for this species.

In conclusion:

Selectivity data exists but still a solution for selectivity improvement in relation to otter trawlers in Div. 8abd has not been reached.

Better results were obtained for pair trawlers, but these selective devices have not been judged worth being implemented by the industry (see WP 2 of Discardless).

4.4.4 Changes in the data collection and processing

Effort is been done aiming at quantifying the used de minimis exemptions and the discard sampling of small pelagics is been strengthened in the last years.

In the period 2016-2018, the only real change has been to adapt the database to the requirement of the landing obligation (to include information of catches under the MCRS and to include information of species subject and not subject to the landing obligation).

In terms of the sampling intensity and or distribution among the different métiers, in the period 2016-2018, no changes have been made, because the fleet in general, except some trips in where mackerel is avoided, has not change its behaviour, and therefore no necessities have been detected on changing the sampling intensity distribution on the métiers. Note that, beyond the small pelagic species, the main target species of this fleet are demersal stocks. For Spain, and in particular for this fleet, the only species which has been under LO has been hake, which is not necessarily a choke species, specifically in this period of high TACs for the northern stock of hake (the target stock of this fleet). Note that this fleet cannot fish in the ICES area 8c, so it has not been subject to the reductions in the TAC of the southern stock of hake.

4.4.5 Changes in discards volumes and fish stocks

The following two tables present the discards estimates in total and by species (%) for the otter fleet (demersal mixed métier).

Table 10. Estimated total catch (tons) and estimated discard percentage by year for otter fleet operating in the Bay of Biscay from the period 2015 to 2017.

Year	Landings (T)	Discards (T)	% discarded
2015	2558	3625	59%
2016	2935	3867	57%
2017	3390	5344	61%

Table 11. Estimated proportion discarded in weight, of the main quota species caught by Basque demersal otter bottom trawlers in the Bay of Biscay (with CVs). In bold, species under TAC and Quota system.

	Percent discarded		
	2015	2016	2017
Horse mackerel	99%	97%	97%
Mackerel	100%	91%	95%
Hake	39%	42%	44%
Blue whiting	99%	96%	94%
Boarfish	100%	100%	100%
Anchovy	100%	100%	100%
Megrim	3%	3%	5%
Nephrops		0%	
Dogfish	67%	57%	56%
Triglids	57%	79%	78%

Results from these tables show how no changes have been detected due to the implementation of the landing obligation in the period 2015-2017.

The following two tables present the discards estimates in total and by species (%) for the pair trawl fleet.

Table 12. Estimated total catch (tons) and total discarded percentage by year for pair trawlers operating in the Bay of Biscay from 2015 to 2017 (95 % CI: confident intervals are presented)

Year	Landings (T)	Discards (T)	% discarded
2015	2485	159	6%
2016	3063	128	4%
2017	3918	141	3%

Table 13. Estimated proportion discarded in weight in relation to total catch of that species caught by Spanish pair bottom trawlers in the Bay of Biscay with CV.

Species	Percent discarded					
	2015		2016		2017	
	2015	CV	2016	CV	2017	CV
Hake	6%	0,3	4%	0,3	4%	56
Horse mackerel	76%	0,5	90%	0,3	66%	0,2
Blue whiting	51%	0,4	89%	0,5	86%	0,5
Haddock	100%	1	100%	0,9	0%	
Mackerel	98%	0,6	96%	0,5	93%	0,4
Boarfish	100%	1	100%	0,9	0%	
Argentine						

In the case of the pair trawlers, an overall reduction of the discards has been detected. However, it is not clear if this is related to the landing obligation (fleet behavioural changes) or to changes in the relative abundance of the species.

4.4.6 Changes in sensitive components of the ecosystem

Marine predators such as seabirds are an especially sensitive community affected by discards due to its importance as a foraging resource; in some cases they can depend exclusively on the abundance of this food resource. The influence of discarding rates and discard composition on seabirds has been assessed, to provide insights on the impact of the Landing Obligation in the Bay of Biscay. Seabird counts on board commercial demersal trawlers operating in ICES subdivision VIIIabd were carried out during the period 2016-2017. These counts established the spatial and

temporal abundance variation of the seabird community associated to trawlers and mark the phenology as the main factor which establishes the presence of the different species in this area. Furthermore, the abundance of seabirds is related to the amount of retained fish, the number of trawlers around and the fishing depth. Additionally, the discard characterization shows the composition of the fishing discards in the area and, considering the fishing policies, the reduction of these in accordance with the regulation. This work provides an essential tool to evaluate management strategies related to discard reduction and the conservation of seabird populations in important wintering areas like the Bay of Biscay (Pedrajas et al., in preparation).

4.5 Eastern Channel case study

4.5.1 Introduction

The case study is focused on the demersal fisheries in the English Eastern Channel. The main fleets described were the French demersal fleets but the English and Belgian fleet were also taken into account in the modelling exercises in WP1 and WP2.

Figure 11: Map of the region covered by the case study (ICES division 27.7.d)

Definitions of métiers are distinct between DCF and annual report of the observer at sea program and the fleet defined in the different DiscardLess WP. The most valuable species landed by French demersal fleets operating in ICES area VIIId are sole (*Solea solea*) and scallops (*Pectens maximus*). The majority of sole landings comes from netters and, to a more limited extent, bottom trawlers and mixed trawlers. Scallops are mainly landed by dredgers. The rest of the value landed by the selected fleets mainly consists in cephalopods, sea bass, whiting, red mullet, cod and plaice.

There are four main métiers involved in demersal fisheries from France:

- OT_DEF bottom trawl trips targeting whitefish benthic fish and cephalopods in ICES division VIIId. This métier targets high value species (i.e. sole, red mullet and cephalopods) or high aggregation of less valuable species like whiting. They use a codend mesh size between 70 and 99 mm. Discards are mainly composed of whiting, plaice, horse mackerel and gurnard. Discard rates can be important depending on the trips, area and seasons.
- G_DEF trips targeting demersal species, cephalopods and crustaceans in ICES division VIIId. This métier includes both GNS and GTR nets and is mostly operated by boats under 13m. Discard rates are quite low (under 10%) and are mostly composed of plaice and spider crabs. The targeted species are flatfish, mostly sole as the most valuable species.
- TBB_DEF is operated by a small number of boats targeting flatfish and switching to scallop dredging in winter. The targeted species is sole and the discard rates can be quite important with spider crab, poor cod and plaice being the main discarding species

- SDN_DEF is operated by an increasing number of boats targeting demersal fish (whiting and red mullet being the most important in tonnage). Discard rates are similar to demersal trawls and are mainly composed of whiting and poor cod.

4.5.2 Adopted discard plan for the region

Fisheries in the Eastern Channel are managed through the EU multiannual management plan (MAP) plan for the Western Waters¹² from 2019. The plan applies to all species subject to catch limits. Some exemption have been provided for:

Survival exemptions

- Survivability exemption for ***common sole***. In ICES division 7d, within six nautical miles of the coast but outside identified nursery areas, the survivability exemption provided for in Article 15(4)(b) of Regulation (EU) No 1380/2013 shall apply to catches of common sole (*Solea solea*) below the minimum conservation reference size made using otter trawl gears (gear codes: OTT, OTB, TBS, TBN, TB, PTB, OT, PT, TX) with a cod end mesh size of 80-99 mm, by vessels: (a) having a maximum length of 10 meters and a maximum engine power of 221 kW; and (b) fishing in waters with the depth of 30 meters or less and with tow durations of no more than 1:30 hours. When discarding common sole, the common sole shall be released immediately.
- Survivability exemption for ***skates and rays***. The survivability exemption provided for in Article 15(4)(b) of Regulation (EU) No 1380/2013 shall apply to total allowable catches of skates and rays (*Rajiformes*) caught by any fishing gear in the North Western Waters (ICES subareas 6 and 7). Member States having a direct management interest shall submit, every year as soon as possible before 31 May, additional scientific information supporting the exemption. The Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries (STECF) shall assess the provided scientific information before 1 August every year. The exemption shall apply to Cuckoo ray until 31 December 2019. Member States having a direct management interest shall submit as soon as possible before 31 May 2019, additional scientific information supporting that exemption. The Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries (STECF) shall assess the provided scientific information before 1 August 2019. When discarding skates and rays, the skates and rays shall be released immediately and below the sea surface.
- Survivability exemption for ***plaice***. The survivability exemption provided for in Article 15(4)(b) of Regulation (EU) No 1380/2013 shall apply to: (a) plaice (*Pleuronectes platessa*) caught in ICES divisions 7d, 7e, 7f and 7g with trammel nets; (b) plaice (*Pleuronectes platessa*) caught in ICES divisions 7d, 7e, 7f and 7g with otter trawls; (c) plaice (*Pleuronectes platessa*) caught in ICES divisions 7a-7k by vessels having a maximum engine greater than 221 kW, and using beam trawls (BT2) fitted with a flip-up rope or benthic release panel; (d) plaice (*Pleuronectes platessa*) caught in ICES divisions 7a-7k by vessels using beam trawls (BT2), having a maximum engine power of 221 kW or a maximum length of 24 meters, which are constructed to fish within 12 nautical miles of the coast and with average tow durations of no more than 1:30 hours. The exemptions referred to in (c) and (d) shall be provisionally applicable until 31 December 2019. Member States having a direct management interest shall submit as soon as possible

¹² EU. 2019. REGULATION (EU) 2019/472 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL establishing a multiannual plan for stocks fished in the Western Waters and adjacent waters, and for fisheries exploiting those stocks, amending Regulations (EU) 2016/1139 and (EU) 2018/973, and repealing Council Regulations (EC) No 811/2004, (EC) No 2166/2005, (EC) No 388/2006, (EC) No 509/2007 and (EC) No 1300/2008. 17pp. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32019R0472>

before 31 May 2019 additional scientific information supporting those exemptions. The Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries shall assess that information before 1 August 2019. When discarding, the plaice shall be released immediately and below the sea surface.

De minimis exemptions

By way of derogation from Article 15(1) of Regulation (EU) No 1380/2013, the following quantities may be discarded pursuant to Article 15(5)(c) of that Regulation:

- (a) for whiting (*Merlangius merlangus*), up to a maximum of 6 % in 2019, and up to a 5 % in 2020 and 2021, of the total annual catches of that species by vessels using bottom trawls and seines with a mesh size equal to or greater than 80 mm (OTB, OTT, OT, PTB, PT, SSC, SDN, SPR, SX, SV, TBN, TBS, TB, TX), pelagic trawls (OTM, PTM) and beam trawls (BT2) with a mesh size of 80-119 mm in ICES division 7d;
- (b) for common sole (*Solea solea*), up to a maximum of 3 % of the total annual catches of that species by vessels using trammel and gill nets to catch common sole in ICES divisions 7d, 7e, 7f and 7g;
- (c) for common sole (*Solea solea*), up to a maximum of 3 % of the total annual catches of that species by vessels using TBB gear with a mesh size of 80-119 mm equipped with Flemish panel, to catch common sole in ICES divisions 7d, 7e, 7f, 7g and 7h;
- (d) for horse mackerel (*Trachurus spp.*), up to a maximum of 7 % in 2019 of the total annual catches of that species by vessels using bottom trawls, seines and beam trawls in ICES subarea 6 and ICES divisions 7b-7k;
- (e) for mackerel (*Scomber scombrus*), up to a maximum of 7 % in 2019 of the total annual catches of that species by vessels using bottom trawls, seines and beam trawls in ICES subarea 6 and ICES divisions 7b-7k. 2.

The de minimis exemptions set out in the points (d)-(d) shall be applicable until 31 December 2019. Member States having a direct management interest shall submit as soon as possible before 31 May 2019, additional scientific information supporting the exemption. The Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries shall assess the provided scientific information before 1 August 2019.

4.5.3 Methods for reducing discard

The general perception is that selectivity can not be increased without losing lots of commercial species in the Eastern Channel. Challenge experiments were run during the DiscardLess project (complementing the national EODE project) but the results of technical or tactical adaptations were not conclusive. The selective devices, as in EODE shown some potentiality to reduce unwanted catches but with associated loss of marketable catch. Spatio-temporal effort reallocation seemed to be highly constrained by regulations, weather, and the abundance of marketable resource.

4.5.4 Changes in the data collection and processing

No change in data collection and processing have been observed yet. The refusal percentage for onboard observer has not been reported to increase since the implementation of the Landing

Obligation but it is hard to predict how things will evolve in the future as the Landing Obligation has not been enforced yet.

4.5.5 Changes in discards volumes and fish stocks

For the Eastern English Channel, assessments (ICES Cat 1 stocks) are available for: Cod (stock distributed over the Eastern Channel and the North Sea), whiting (stock distributed over the Eastern Channel and the North Sea), sole, plaice, sea bass (central and southern North Sea, Irish Sea, English Channel, Bristol Channel, and Celtic Sea).

Cod .27.47d20

Currently fished above F_{MSY} and between F_{pa} and F_{lim}, SSB MSY Btrigger and between B_{pa} and B_{lim}

whg.27.47d

Currently fished above FMSY but below Fpa and Flim; spawning-stock size is above MSY Btrigger, Bpa, and Blim.

sol.27.7d

Currently fished below FMSY, Fpa, and Flim; and spawning-stock size is below MSY Btrigger and between Bpa and Blim.

sol.27.7d

Currently fished below F_{MSY}, F_{pa}, and F_{lim}; spawning-stock size is above MSY Btrigger, B_{pa}, and B_{lim}.

bss.27.4bc7ad-h

Currently fished below F_{MSY}, F_{pa}, and F_{lim}, and that the spawning-stock size is below MSY Btrigger, B_{pa}, and B_{lim}.

Biseau 2019 made a summary of the stock status of the stock exploited by the French fleets in the English Eastern Channel and the North Sea and its evolution between 2017 and 2018. He classified the landings based on the ICES status of the different stocks either not assessed („non évaluées“), not classified („non classifié“) if the reference points are not defined, overfished („surpêchés“) if the assessed biomass is under the biomass reference point or well exploited („bien pêchés“) if the assessed biomass is over the biomass reference point.

Figure 12: Fraction of the French landings coming from stock classified under different status (2017)

Figure 13: Fraction of the French landings coming from stock classified under different status (2018)

Between 2017 and 2018, the french landings in the North Sea and Eastern English Channel landings increased by 2%. The fraction of landings coming from "well exploited" stock increased because of the change in status of scallop and squid that were unclassified in 2017 but classified as "well exploited" in 2018.

4.6 Azores case study

4.6.1 Introduction

The Azores is an oceanic archipelago in the mid North Atlantic Ocean, between the continental Europe and North America. With the absence of a continental shelf and surrounding great depths, fishing occurs around the island slopes and the many seamounts present in its vast exclusive economic zone of 1 million km² (Silva and Pinho, 2007; Morato et al., 2008). The Azorean fishing industry is composed of five main components (Pham et al. 2013):

- i) bottom longline and handline fishery targeting mainly deep-sea demersal fishes such as blackspot seabream (*Pagellus bogaraveo*), wreckfish (*Polyprion americanus*), alfonsinos (*Beryx* spp.) or blackbelly rosefish (*Helicolenus dactylopterus*);
- ii) drifting deep-water longline fishery for black scabbardfish (*Aphanopus carbo*)
- iii) a pole-and-line tuna fishery, and its associated livebait fishery;
- iv) a pelagic longline fishery targeting swordfish (*Xiphias gladius*) and pelagic sharks;
- v) a small-net fishery for small pelagic species (blue jack mackerel, *Trachurus picturatus*, and chub mackerel, *Scomber colias*).

The Azores cases study focuses only on the deep-water hook and lines gears targeting benthic or benthopelagic fish; such as the bottom longline and handline fishery and the drifting deep-water longline fishery for black scabbardfish.

4.6.1.1 Bottom hook and line gears (handline and longline)

The bottom hook-and-line gears (handline and longline) are the most important fishery in the region both in terms of landed value, number of boats and jobs (Carvalho et al., 2011). With over 80% of vessels <12m, it is considered a small scale fishery operating all year round from coastal areas to offshore seamounts. With an average estimated catch (including unreported and discards) of about 4500 t·year⁻¹ over the period 2008-2017 (Figure 14) that includes more than 20 species with economic value, discards were expected to represent 11.0% of this amount, i.e. 510 t·year⁻¹ (Figure 1). Species with high discard amounts included the silver scabbardfish (*Lepidopus caudatus*) and European conger (*Conger conger*) due to the low economic value of small individuals, and blackbelly rosefish and alfonsinos, especially in years when the TAC was exceeded (Table 14). It was suggested that the establishment of the TAC system for this multispecific bottom fishery greatly increased discard rates of deep-sea species without decreasing catch levels (Pham et al., 2013). Such unreported mortality undermines the effectiveness of the TAC system to manage those species. The *Beryx* quota has been reached increasingly earlier in the recent years, and resulted in increased discard of this fishery. The quota of blackspot seabream, that is individual in most islands of the archipelago, has never been reached. Yet, catch and discard of undersize blackspot seabreams still occurs regularly. Discard of undersize blackspot seabream and alfonsinos, quota species, would likely be limiting under the LO and mitigation measures would be needed.

Figure 14: Time series of catch volume of the bottom longline and handline fishery, segregated between reported catch (i.e. official landings; in black), unreported discards (white) and unreported catch for other uses (including bait; in grey).

4.6.1.2 Deep water drifting longline fishery

Drifting deep-water longline targeting black scabbardfish is still considered an experimental deep-water fishery in the Azores. In 2017 only a few vessels registered in Madeira island operated inside the Azores EEZ and no fishing vessels were involved in this fishery in 2018. This fishery started to be experimented in the Azores in 1998. In the last 10 years landings were small but have peaked at 450t in 2012 (Figure 6). According to a report prepared by Ramos et al. (2013) in 2010 there might have been about 10 fishing vessels with a mean length of 14m operating the drifting deep-water longline in the Azores. Due to both technical and market difficulties, this number has likely diminished since. Bycatch species of this fishery accounted for about 17.4% of the total catch. Discards were estimated to represent only 2.0% of the total catch of the fishery. In the Azores as in other regions, deep sea sharks composed the main bycatch (Machete et al., 2011), mainly leafscale gulper shark and the Portuguese dogfish. Other species reported as bycatch of this fishery but with low numbers include *Etmopterus* sp., *Mora moro*, *Deania cf. calcea*, *Centroscymnus crepidater*, *Alepocephalus rostratus*, *Deania profundorum* and *Chiasmodon niger*. There is a growing concern with the bycatch of some of these species and Machete et al. (2011) suggested that those catches should be closely monitored in the future if the fishery is to be expanded in the Azores.

Figure 15: Time series of catch volume of the deep-water drifting longline fishery, segregated between reported catch (i.e. official landings; in black), unreported discards (white) and unreported catch for other uses (including bait; in grey). Catch of Madeira registered vessels fishing inside the Azores EEZ were not accounted in the unreported catch yet.

4.6.1.3 Summary of existing regulations

The current fishery resource management strategy of the Azores is based on the EU CFP, implemented primarily through total allowable catches (TACs) for various species (Table 14) including blackspot seabream, alfonsinos, and deepwater sharks such as *Deania* spp., *Centrophorus* spp., *Etmopterus* spp., *Centroscymnus* spp., and kitefin shark (*Dalatias licha*) (EC Reg. 2340/2002; EC Reg. 2270/2004). For blackspot seabream, there are individual fishing non-transferable quotas in some islands, collective quotas in some other islands, and a combination of both in Faial and São Miguel islands. For all the other species and islands the quotas are collective to all vessels, of which mainly alfonsinos (*Beryx* spp.) and greater forkbeard (*Phycis blennoides*) are of interest for the bottom longline and handline fishery, and black scabbardfish (*Aphanopus carbo*) for the deep-water drifting longline. The quota of alfonsinos is set for both species together, *Beryx splendens* and *B. decadactylus* and has been reduced and reached earlier in the recent years (Table 14). To better manage this quota and limit the socio-economic impacts and since *B. decadactylus* is less frequent and have higher commercial value than *B. splendens*, a “80% notice” has been implemented since 2013. It means that whenever 80% of the quota of the complex is reached, the catch of *B. splendens* is not allowed anymore while up to 5% of *B. decadactylus* in the total catch can still be landed.

For deep-water sharks, a TAC 0 has been implemented since 2010 for over 13 taxa (Table 14, EC_1359-2008). A TAC 0 has also been implemented for orange roughy (*Hoplostethus atlanticus*), but since 2017 the species has been declared “prohibited species” implying that under the LO all catch must be discarded. While for deep-water sharks that are still under TAC 0, to date, it remains unsure how their catch would have to be handled under the LO.

Table 14: Summary of changes in management measures affecting the bottom longline and handline and deep-water drifting longline targeting black scabbardfish (DLL) fisheries, and quota species they catch, since 2010.

Measure	Species	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Quota	<i>Beryx spp.</i>	214t	214t	214t	203t; "80% notice"	193t; "80% notice"	193t; "80% notice"	193t; "80% notice"	182t; "80% notice"	182t; "80% notice"
MLS	<i>Beryx splendens</i>	-	-	-	-	-	250 g	250 g	30 cm	30 cm
MLS	<i>Beryx decadactylus</i>						250 g	250 g	35 cm	35 cm
Quota	<i>Pagellus bogaraveo</i>	1116t	1116t	1116t	1104t	904t	678t	507t	507t	507t
MLS	<i>Pagellus bogaraveo</i>	25 cm	25 cm	25 cm	25 cm	25 cm	30 cm	32 cm	33 cm	33 cm
Seasonal closure	<i>Pagellus bogaraveo</i>	-	-	-	-	-	15/01 to 29/02	15/01 to 29/02	15/01 to 31/01**	-
Quota	<i>Phycis blennoides</i>	36t	36t	36t	36t	36t	45t	45t	40t	36t
Quota	<i>Hoplostethus atlanticus</i>	TAC 0	TAC 0	TAC 0	TAC 0	TAC 0	TAC 0	TAC 0	Prohibited species	Prohibited species
Quota	<i>Aphanopus carbo</i> ***	3311 t	3311 t	3311 t	3659 t	3689 t	3659 t	3659 t	3294 t	2965 t
Quota	13 taxa**** of deep-water sharks (DWS)	Implementation of the TAC 0; allowance of max 10% of 2009 quota (10t) as bycatch	TAC 0; allowance of max 3% of 2009 quota (10t) taken as bycatch; 4 new species added*****	TAC 0	TAC 0; <i>Galeus melastomus</i> removed; <i>Centrophorus lusitanicus</i> added	TAC 0	TAC 0	TAC 0	TAC 0; allowance of 10t of bycatch only of DLL; no directed fishery allowed	TAC 0; allowance of 10t of bycatch only of DLL; no directed fishery allowed

* "80% notice" occurs when 80% of the shared *Beryx spp.* quota has been achieved and implies a 5% catch limit for *B. decadactylus* and a closure for *B. splendens*.

** A new regulation 13/2017 approved by the Regional Government of the Azores revoked the seasonal closure for *Pagellus bogaraveo*.

*** The black scabbard fish quota presented here is for areas XIII, IX and X which includes mainland Portugal and the Azores. The Madeira quota is included in the CECAF 34.1.2. area.

**** List of deep-water sharks (DWS) for which a TAC 0 has been applied since 2010: *Apristurus spp.*, *Centrophorus granulosus*, *Centrophorus squamosus*, *Centroscyllium fabricii*, *Centroscymnus coelolepis*, *Centroscymnus crepidater*, *Dalatias licha*, *Deania calcea*, *Etmopterus princeps*, *Etmopterus spinax*, *Galeus melastomus*, *Galeus murinus*, *Somniosus microcephalus*.

***** *Chlamydoselachus anguineus*, *Hexanchus griseus*, *Oxynotus paradoxus*, *Scymnodon ringens* added.

Apart from the quotas system, the regional government of the Azores has implemented technical measures over the years, such as minimum landing sizes or weights (some – not all- examples are shown in Table 14), minimum mesh and hook sizes, limitation of licences for some specific gears, area and temporal closures, and bans on the use of specific gear. An example is the regulation that prohibited deep-sea trawling in the Azores, Madeira and Canary Islands which became an EC regulation (EC 1568/2005). Also, a one 100 miles polygon around the islands limiting the fishing to vessels registered in the Azores was created in 2003 (EC Reg. 1954/2003), and revised in 2013 (EC 1380/2013) until December 2022. Other spatio-temporal limitations applying to the bottom longline and handline fishery include a seasonal fishing closure for blackspot seabream that has been implemented in one to two winter months in January and/or February from 2015 to 2017 (Portaria N.74-2015, Portaria N.88-2016, Portaria N.13-2017). This closure was amended in 2017. Others fishing restrictions relative to gear type have also been implemented for bottom longliners and handliners (Regulamento Portaria 50/2012, de 27/04 Anexo I): i) longliners are not allowed to fish within 3 nm from shore, ii) longliners may only fish from 3 to 6 nm from shore in São Miguel and Terceira but only for the vessels registered in those islands or having them as home ports, while in the other islands such allowance was only given in some period; iii) for handliners, vessels $\leq 14\text{m}$ are not allowed within 1 nm from the coast, this limit is set to 3 nm for the vessels $>14\text{m}$, and 30 nm for vessels $>24\text{m}$.

Although stock assessment methods and abundance indices show somehow healthy stocks of demersal deep-water species in the Azores (ICES, 2018), there is a common perception among fishers that some stocks may be facing serious problems. Additionally, local fishers fear that open access regime under the current CFP reforms will allow foreign vessels to decimate their fish stocks (Carvalho et al., 2011). They argue that they are an ultra-remote island community, with fragile resources and economies and many rural communities heavily dependent on the fishing sector for their economic wellbeing (Carvalho et al., 2011). They need special recognition and special protection from the threats of open access and free-for-all fishing, which would encourage over-exploitation of fish stocks. Additionally, there are some concerns on the potential exploitation of demersal fish stocks outside the Azores EEZ by international trawlers.

4.6.2 Adopted discard plan for the region and fisheries of interest

Only two discard plans have already been adopted for the South-Western Waters that are relevant to fisheries in Azores (ICES sub-area X). Those plans were adopted for the deep-water black scabbardfish (EU 2017/2167, EU 2018/44) and for small pelagic mackerels (EU 2018/44).

In May 2018, the Regional Government of the Azores (RGA) submitted to the Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries (STECF) secretariat, a document, for each request, “Supporting evidence for requesting exemption to the landing obligation of Azorean bottom longline and handline (hooks and lines) fishery in Central North Atlantic Waters (ICES sub-area X).” The Azores Case study of the Discardless project provided scientific information by request of the RGA. Exemptions of the LO were asked for the hooks and lines (LHP, LHM, LLS, LLD) fisheries in ICES sub-area X:

- *De minimis* exemption for alfonosinos (*Beryx spp.*)
- *De minimis* exemption for greater forkbeard (*Phycis blennoides*)
- High survival exemption of blackspot seabream (*Pagellus bogaraveo*)

For each request, a supporting document was provided with an exhaustive description of Azores fisheries together with a full list of management measures. The requests included a series of historical trends of landing and discards data. Analyses of discards were made with data obtained from the DCF and from the EU funded Discardless project (STECF, 2018).

For alfonosinos (*Beryx spp.*) caught by hooks and lines in ICES sub-area X, a 5% *de minimis* exemption was requested. The supporting document pointed out that difficulties in further increasing selectivity arise because longline fishing is already very selective. The *de minimis* request was also made on the grounds of socio-economic issues mainly relating to the fact this fishery operates in one of the outermost regions where the economy is based on the activity of this fleet and where there are distance and market obstacles to overcome. Avoidance measures of the species concerned are already used in the region include technical and tactical strategies and this has contributed to a decrease in the catch of alfonosinos. The EWG 18-06 considered that on the basis of the evidence presented the justification for difficulties on the grounds of selectivity or disproportionate costs are supported (STECF, 2018).

Roughly the same arguments were presented for greater forkbeard (*Phycis blennoides*) caught by hooks and lines in ICES sub-area X, for which the allocation of 3% *de minimis* exemption was requested. A table displaying information on catch and discards for all species contributing to over 1% of the total catch of the bottom longline and handline was included in the document; where greater forkbeard does not appear as catches are very low. The STECF EWG 18-06 considered that on the basis of the evidence presented the justification for difficulties on the grounds of selectivity or disproportionate costs are supported (STECF, 2018).

For blackspot seabream (*Pagellus bogaraveo*) caught in ICES subareas X with hooks and lines, a high survival exemption was requested. Two sources of information were used: i) Results from onboard observer data (413 individual fish) were presented showing a 76% vigorous vitality status (strength in its body, moves without stimulus and is able to do a 'tail-flip', strong swimming towards the bottom when released) for blackspot seabreams caught with deep-water bottom longline and 73% for the blackspot seabreams caught with handlines. These results suggest a reasonably high post-release survival probability but do not provide information on the medium to longer term survival outcomes since these were not monitored; ii) Results from an acoustic and satellite telemetry tagging programme (in place since 2001) were presented showing a 67% survival, 8 days after capture. The data presented here represent a directly demonstrated high survival rate of fish discarded carefully under experimental conditions. Whether this is representative of the typical treatment in the commercial fishery is not clear. The STECF EWG 18-06 considered that the studies represent reasonably sound scientific evidence for the survival of blackspot seabream following discarding (STECF, 2018).

Table 15: Discard plans already adopted for South-Western Waters that are relevant to fisheries in ICES sub-area X.

Species	Fishing zones	Fishing gear	Species to be landed	Regulation
Black scabbardfish (<i>Aphanopus carbo</i>)	ICES divisions VIIIc, IX, X and CECAF zone 34.1.2	Deepwater set-longlines	All catches of black scabbardfish where the total landings per vessel of all species in 2014 and 2015 (1) consisted of more than 20 % of black scabbardfish	EU 2018/44 of 20 October 2017 (published in 12/1/2018)
Black scabbardfish (<i>Aphanopus carbo</i>)	CES divisions VIIIc, IX, X and CECAF zone 34.1.2	Deepwater set-longlines	All catches of black scabbardfish	EU 2017/2167 of 5 July 2017
Horse mackerel, jack mackerel and mackerels	ICES divisions VIII, IX, X and CECAF divisions 34.1.1, 34.1.2, 34.2.0	Purse seines	Up to a maximum of 4 % in 2018, 2019 and 2020 of the total annual catches of horse mackerel, jack mackerel and mackerel	EU 2018/188 of 21 November 2017 (published in 9/2/2018)

4.6.3 Methods for reducing discards

A main change that is taking place in the Azores bottom fishery since 2000 is the increased conversion of bottom longliners to handliners (Figure 16); which were shown to have reduced unwanted catch, mainly of the TAC 0 deep-water sharks, and therefore contributes to discard avoidance. Handlines were also demonstrated to have slight improved survival for most species including the blackspot seabream (Figure 16). This change bottom longliners to handliners partly results from the banning of the use of bottom longlines at distances less than 3 nm from the coast, and non-renewal of some fishing licenses for bottom longliners by the Regional Government of the Azores.

Figure 16.: Number of fishing licenses granted by the Regional Government of the Azores (left) to bottom longliners (in grey) and handliners (in black) from 2005 to 2018 (unpub. data); and the vitality status of the blackspot seabream sampled after catch with deep-water bottom longlines (BLL) and handlines (HL) in the Azores (right; DiscardLess unpub. data).

As part of the DiscardLess project, semi-interviews were performed with fishers from the bottom longline and handline fishery. Among other topics, they were asked about their fishing practices,

and current practices they employ to avoid unwanted catch, both technical (i.e. gear-based), and tactical (i.e. based on fishing strategies). From those interviews, it appears that fishers already take several actions to limit the amount of unwanted catch:

Fishing strategies several fishers already apply to avoid unwanted catch include:

- Three out of seven handline fishers interviewed used to fish with the bottom longline and had recently changed for handline. They explained that the reasons for this change were also economic. The handlines catch less fish, but bigger individuals, they can sell for a higher price. Further the expenses (hook, bait, and crew) are also much lower for this gear. It results that the handlines have a better cost-effectiveness than longlines. With higher selectivity and lower discard of handline compared to longlines, this conversion also contributes to better avoidance of unwanted catch.
- Changing fishing areas when high proportions of small individuals are caught: which is faster for handliners which after 1 or 2 sets catching small individuals would change area, while for longliners as the whole set lasts around 1 day, the change of area can only occur the following day;
- Adapting their fishing depth: if fishing deeper they would catch fewer but bigger blackspot seabreams, they would also catch (more) alfonsinos (*Beryx spp.*) and deep-water sharks;
- Adapting their fishing time: sunset and sunrise are the best times to fish, avoiding fishing during the night as there is more predation; smaller fish are also caught during new moon.

The bottom longline and handline fishery is very selective, and most fishers feel they are already using one of the most selective fishing gears in the whole European Union. Still, several fishers performed some **alterations of fishing gears** to better avoid unwanted catch including:

- Using large hook size: according to almost all fishers this is the most efficient way to reduce the amount of undersize fish caught. Hook n° 9 (i.e. the legal size) is already used by most fishers, some fishers even use bigger hook (from n°8 to n°5), however some fishers recognised using smaller hooks to catch more;
- Using different hook shape: some fishers are using “Spanish” hooks, which are (still) J-hooks but more curved, and feel them to be efficient to reduce the unwanted catch. No scientific evidence confirms it though.

4.6.4 Changes in the data collection and processing

As far as we are aware no changes were introduced in the official data collection and processing. However, the DiscardLess project implemented a fisheries observer program in 2017 in collaboration with the POPA (the Observer Program for Azores Fisheries) and the data collection team. The fisheries observer program was first planned to be implemented on the drifting longliners targeting black scabbardfish in Azorean waters, but as this fishery is currently not taking place in the Azores, it was decided that the observer program would focus on the bottom longline and handline fishery instead. The objectives of the program were to monitor the changes in discard practices due to i) the deep-sea shark 0 quota (ongoing but a new fleet is coming in to fish black scabbardfish), ii) the blackspot seabream minimum size (ongoing) and seasonal closure (new in 2015), and iii) quota species (mostly blackspot seabream and alfonsinos). Yet, this

program did not monitor changes induced by the LO since the LO will only be implemented in 2019 in the Azores demersal fishery.

4.6.5 Changes in discards volumes and fish stocks

Since the LO is only planned to be implemented in 2019 in the Azores demersal fishery, the changes in fishing and discard practices documented through the observer program implemented in 2017 were not induced by the LO. The recent increase in MLS for blackspot seabream and decrease in quotas for blackspot seabream and alfonsinos implemented by the Regional Government of the Azores have resulted in increased discard by this fishery in the recent years. But it is expected that the exemptions requested by the Regional Government of the Azores for those species would help mitigate the impacts of the LO in this fishery.

4.6.6 Changes in sensitive components of the ecosystem

Bycatch from the bottom longline and drifting longline fisheries are of concern because they include many deep-water sharks listed in the IUCN red list of endangered species. For example, the “critically endangered” gulper shark (*Centrophorus granulosus*), blue skate (*Dipturus batis*), the “endangered” kitefin shark (*Dalatias licha*), Portuguese dogfish (*Centroscymnus coelolepis*), leafscale gulper shark (*Centrophorus squamosus*); birdbeak dogfish (*Deania calcea*); the “near threatened” greenland shark (*Somniosus microcephalus*), and the “least concern” longnose velvet dogfish (*Centroscymnus crepidater*) (IUCN Europe 2018 - The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species. Version 2018-1).

In the bottom longline and handline fishery, deep-water sharks are represented by at least ten species and accounted for 8% of the discards in the recent years (2010-2014; Fauconnet et al. subm.). In the drifting deep-water longline fishery in the Azores as in other regions, deep sea sharks are the main by-catch, mainly leafscale gulper shark and the Portuguese dogfish (Machete et al., 2011, Ramos et al., 2013). Despite this fishery still being in an experimental phase in the Azores, there is a growing concern with the bycatch of some of these species and close monitoring would be required if the fishery is to be expanded in the Azores (Machete et al., 2011), which has not happened yet.

As the result of their vulnerability, a TAC 0 was implemented on many deep-water sharks since 2010 by the EC (Table 14). Yet the catch of those species still occurs occasionally and some of this bycatch is used as bait. Further as a market value still exist on shark liver oil, some catch also remains kept and sold for this use. Fishers argue deep-water sharks are very abundant and difficult to avoid. By adapting their fishing depth and by using handlines, bycatch can be avoided but only partially. In 2017, a bycatch allowance of 10 t per year was granted to the drifting deep-water longliners. To date, it remains unclear how the catch of deep-water sharks (TAC 0 species) would have to be handled under the LO. With the upcoming implementation of the LO, those issues turn out to be even more decisive as deep-water shark could rapidly choke those fisheries and have heavy socio-economic impacts for those fisheries and for the whole region.

4.7 North Sea and West of Scotland

This case study focusses on demersal fisheries in the North Sea and waters to the west of Scotland (ICES SA 4 & 6).

Figure 17. ICES Statistical areas 4 (North Sea) and 6 (West of Scotland)

4.7.1 Fisheries

Around 7000 vessels from nine nations operate in the Greater North Sea and to the West of Scotland, with the largest numbers coming from UK, Norway, Denmark, the Netherlands, and France. Total landings peaked in the early 1970s and have since declined. Of these, the largest sector of the fleet are demersal otter trawlers, with significant numbers of beam trawls, dredges and seine netters. A small number of large vessels fish for the pelagic species (herring, mackerel and blue whiting) found in the area. Since 2003, total fishing effort has declined, however profitability of many of the commercial fleets has increased in recent years due to the improved status of many fish stocks, reduced fleet sizes, lower fuel prices, and more efficient fishing gears

Belgium

The Belgian fishing fleet operating in the North Sea is composed of about 75 vessels, primarily beam trawlers both above and below 24 m in length. Few vessels are smaller than 12 m. Most of the catch is demersal species, with sole the dominant species by value, and plaice the dominant species in volume. Other significant species include lemon sole, turbot, anglerfish, rays, cod, shrimp, and scallops.

Denmark

The Danish North Sea demersal fleet comprises around 600 vessels. Smaller vessels (< 12 m) constitute the greatest proportion of the fleet, but account for less than 5% of the Danish fisheries catch value. The most important demersal fisheries target cod, plaice, saithe, northern shrimp, and *Nephrops* using bottom trawls and seines.

France

The French demersal fleet in the North Sea is also composed of around 600 vessels. These operate mainly in the eastern English Channel and southern North Sea, targeting a variety of finfish and shellfish species. The largest fleet segments are gill- and trammel netters (10–18 m) targeting sole, demersal trawlers (12–24 m) catching a great diversity of fish and cephalopod species, and dredgers catching scallops. Smaller boats operate different gears throughout the year and target different species assemblages. A further fleet of six large demersal trawlers (>40 m) target saithe in the northern North Sea and to the west of Scotland. In waters to the west of Scotland (Division 6.a) around ten bottom trawlers have historically targetted deep-sea fish,. Finally, a small number of vessels target hake using longlines or nets in this area.

Germany

The German North Sea fishing fleet comprises more than 200 vessels. Beam trawlers constitute the largest fleet component (around 180 vessels, 12–24 m) and target brown shrimp in the southern North Sea. Six large demersal trawlers (>40 m) target saithe in the northern North Sea (and in waters to the north of the North Sea). Several mid-sized otter trawlers and beam trawlers (24–40 m) target saithe, cod, sole, and plaice.

Netherlands

The Dutch fleet in the North Sea consists of about 500 vessels. The main demersal fleet is the beam trawl fleet (275 vessels, of which 85 are >24 m and 190 are < 24 m) operating in the southern and central North Sea, and, like the Belgian fleet, targeting sole (dominant in value) and plaice (dominant in volume). Most of the smaller beam trawlers seasonally target shrimp or flatfish.

Norway

The Norwegian North Sea demersal fleet is composed of about 1300 vessels. These target a combination of fish, crustaceans, cephalopods, and elasmobranchs. Approximately 60% of this fleet are small vessels (< 10 m) that operate near the Norwegian coast using static gears (traps, pots, and gillnets) to target crabs, squid, and several fish species. Medium-sized vessels (10– 24 m) mainly target *Nephrops*, shrimp using trawls, and cod, saithe, ling, and monkfish using gillnets. The offshore fleet (>40 m) is predominantly otter trawlers, but also includes seiners and longliners. Larger vessels (>24 m) account for most of the landings of saithe, ling, cod, tusk, hake, haddock, herring, blue whiting, mackerel, and sprat. To the west of Scotland, a small number of vessels target ling, blue ling and torsk using long lines.

Sweden

The Swedish fleet in the Greater North Sea comprises more than 500 vessels. The demersal fleet is highly diversified, catching several species in the Kattegat and Skagerrak, mainly *Nephrops*, northern shrimp, cod, witch, flounder, and saithe.

United Kingdom

The English fleet in the Greater North Sea has more than 1120 vessels. Around 1000 active vessels of <10m operate in the eastern English Channel and coastal North Sea, catching a diverse assemblage of fish and shellfish species. Medium-size demersal trawlers (80 vessels, 18– 24 m and 24–40 m) primarily target *Nephrops*, cod, and whiting, while around 40 medium and large beam trawlers account for the major share of the plaice landings.

The Scottish North Sea fleet comprises around 1000 vessels. More than 120 demersal trawlers (almost all >10 m) fish for mixed gadoids (cod, haddock, whiting, saithe, and hake,) and for groundfish such as anglerfish and megrim. A fleet of 116 trawlers fish mainly for *Nephrops* in the North Sea: 37 of these vessels (< 10 m) operate on the inshore grounds, while 79 (>10 m) operate over various offshore grounds. Scallop fishing is carried out by around 70 dredgers (mostly >10 m). Limited amounts of longlining and gill netting are also conducted by Scottish vessels. The remainder are smaller (<10m) inshore vessels primarily targeting *Nephrops* and crabs using pots. Most fishing activity by Scottish vessels (754 boats in 2015) occurs in Subarea 6. Around 62 demersal trawlers (mostly >10 m) fish for mixed gadoids and benthic species such as anglerfish and megrim. A small number of boats target haddock at Rockall. In inshore areas, a fleet of 164 trawlers fish mainly for *Nephrops* – 34 of these boats are under 10 m. Scallop fishing is carried out by around 50 dredgers (mostly > 10 m) and by hand gathering (diving). Limited amounts of inshore longlining and gillnetting are also carried out.

4.7.2 Adopted Discard Reduction Plan for the Region

The Landings Obligation was implemented gradually in the North Sea from 1 January 2016 for all fisheries for cod, haddock, whiting, saithe, *Nephrops*, common sole, plaice; hake and Northern prawn. To the west of Scotland it was introduced gradually in fisheries for cod, haddock, whiting, saithe, Norway lobster, common sole, plaice and hake on 1 January 2016. On both areas, on 1 January 2019, all other quota regulated species became subject to the landings obligation.

It is still possible to discard certain species where *de minimis* conditions can be demonstrated or where certain species can be demonstrated to have a high degree of survivability when discarded, as detailed below.

a) Fisheries in Union waters of ICES subarea 4, and divisions 2a and 3a

Fishery	Gear Code	Fishing gear description	Mesh Size	Landing Obligation
Common sole	GN, GNS, GND, GNC, GTN, GTR, GEN, GNF	Trammel and gill nets	All	<i>De minimis</i> exemption allowing discarding of a quantity of common sole below and above the minimum conservation reference size, which shall not exceed 3 % of the total annual catches of that species.
Common sole	TBB	Beam trawl	80-119mm	<i>De minimis</i> exemption allowing discarding of a quantity of common sole below minimum conservation reference sizes, which shall not exceed 6 % of the total annual catches of that species in 2019 and 5 % the rest of the period.
Norway lobster (<i>Nephrops Norvegicus</i>)	OTB, TBN	Bottom trawls equipped with a species-selective grid with a bar spacing of maximum 35 mm in Union waters of ICES division 3a	≥70m	<i>De minimis</i> exemption allowing discarding of a combined quantity of common sole, haddock, whiting, cod, saithe and hake below the minimum conservation reference size, which shall not exceed 4 % of the total annual catches of Norway lobster, common sole, haddock, whiting and Northern prawn, cod, saithe and hake;
Northern prawn	OTB	Bottom trawls equipped with a species selective grid with a bar spacing of maximum 19 mm, and with unblocked fish outlet, in Union waters of ICES division 3a	≥35 mm	<i>De minimis</i> exemption allowing discarding of a combined quantity of common sole, haddock, whiting, cod, plaice, saithe, herring, Norway pout, greater silver smelt and blue whiting below minimum conservation reference size, which shall not exceed 5 % of the total annual catches of Norway lobster, common sole, haddock, whiting, cod, saithe, plaice, Northern prawn, hake, Norway pout, greater silver smelt, herring and blue whiting
Mixed demersal fisheries	OTB, OTT, SDN, SSC	Bottom trawls or seines in Union waters of division 4c	70-99mm	<i>De minimis</i> exemption allowing discarding of a combined quantity of whiting and cod below minimum conservation reference sizes, which shall not

				exceed 6 % of the total annual catches in 2019 and 5 % in 2020 and 2021 of species below minimum reference size that would fall under landing obligation; the maximum amount of cod that may be discarded shall be limited to 2 % of those total annual catches;
Mixed demersal fisheries	OTB, OTT, SDN, SSC	Bottom trawls or seines in Union waters of division 4a and 4b	70-99mm	<i>De minimis</i> exemption allowing discarding of a combined quantity of whiting and cod below minimum conservation reference size, which shall not exceed 6 % of the total annual catches in 2019 of species below minimum reference size that would fall under landing obligation; the maximum amount of cod that may be discarded shall be limited to 2 % of those total annual catches;
All fisheries	OTB, OTT, TBN	Bottom trawls in Union waters of division 3a	90 – 119mm (equipped with a Seltra panel) or >=120 mm	<i>De minimis</i> exemption allowing discarding of a quantity of whiting below minimum conservation reference sizes, up to a maximum of 2 % of the total annual catches of Norway lobster, cod, haddock, whiting, saithe, common sole, plaice and hake;
Norway lobster (<i>Nephrops norvegicus</i>)	OTB, OTT, TBN	Bottom trawls equipped with a SepNep in Union waters of Subarea 4	80-99mm	<i>De minimis</i> exemption allowing discarding of a quantity of plaice below the minimum conservation reference size, which shall not exceed 3 % of the total annual catches of saithe, plaice, haddock, whiting, cod, Northern prawn, common sole and Norway lobster;
Brown shrimp	TB, TBB	Beam trawls in Union waters of Divisions 4b and 4c		<i>De minimis</i> exemption allowing discarding of a quantity of all species subject to catch limits, which shall not exceed 7 % in 2019 and 2020, 6 % in 2021 of the total annual catches of all species subject to catch limits;

Ling	OTB, OTT, PTB	Bottom trawls in Union waters of Subarea 4	>= 100mm	<i>De minimis</i> exemption allowing discarding of a quantity of ling below minimum conservation reference size, which shall not exceed 3 % of the total annual catches of ling in that fishery
Mixed demersal fisheries	TB, TBB	Beam trawls in Union waters of Subarea 4	80 – 119mm	<i>De minimis</i> exemption allowing discarding of a quantity of whiting below minimum conservation reference size, which shall not exceed 2 % of the total annual catches of plaice and sole
Mixed demersal fisheries	OTB, OTT, PTB, TBB	Bottom trawls in Subarea 4	80 – 99mm	<i>De minimis</i> exemption allowing discarding of a quantity of horse mackerel, which shall not exceed 7 % in 2019 of the total annual catches in that fishery of horse mackerel
Mixed demersal fisheries	OTB, OTT, PTB, TBB	Bottom trawls in Subarea 4	80 – 99mm	<i>De minimis</i> exemption allowing discarding of a quantity of horse mackerel, which shall not exceed 7 % in 2019 of the total annual catches in that fishery of mackerel

Specific technical measures are in place for the Skaggeiak, namely the prohibition of trawls or seines with a mesh size of less than 120mm, with exemptions for trawls with a cod-end mesh size of at least 90 mm, if they are equipped with a Seltra panel or a sorting grid with no more than 35 mm bar spacing; trawls with a cod-end mesh size of at least 70 mm which are equipped with a sorting grid with no more than 35 mm bar spacing; and trawls with a minimum mesh sizes of less than 70 mm when fishing for pelagic or industrial species, provided the catch contains more than 80 % of one or more pelagic or industrial species.

Trawls with a cod-end of at least 35 mm mesh size are allowed to be used when fishing for Northern prawn, provided the trawl is equipped with a sorting grid with a maximum bar spacing of 19 mm. A fish retention device may be used in this context, provided there are adequate fishing opportunities to cover by-catch and that the retention device is constructed with a top panel with a minimum mesh size of 120 mm square mesh; is at least 3 metres long; and is at least as wide as the sorting grid itself.

b) fisheries in Union and international waters of Subarea 6

Fishery	Gear Code	Fishing gear description	Mesh Size	Landing Obligation
Norway lobster	FPO, FX	Pots, traps and creels	All	High survivability exemption allowing discarding of Norway lobster caught in Subarea 6 using pots and creels
	OTB, OTT, TBN	Otter trawls	80-110mm	High survivability exemption allowing discarding of Norway lobster caught within 12 nautical miles of the coast in Division 6a using highly selective gears detailed below.
Skates & Rays		All gears		High survivability exemption allowing discarding of skates and rays caught by any gears.
All fish species	FPO, FX	Pots, traps and creels	All	High survivability exemption allowing discarding of all fish species caught in pots, traps and creels.
Horse mackerel	OTB, OTT, OT, PTB, PT, SSC, SDN, SPR, SX, SV, TBN, TBS, TB, TX	Otter trawls, beam trawls and seines		<i>De minimis</i> exemption in 2019 allowing discarding of a quantity of horse mackerel up to 7% of total annual catches of this species by vessels using these gears.
Mackerel	OTB, OTT, OT, PTB, PT, SSC, SDN, SPR, SX, SV, TBN, TBS, TB, TX	Otter trawls, beam trawls and seines		<i>De minimis</i> exemption in 2019 allowing discarding of a quantity of mackerel up to 7% of total annual catches of this species by vessels using these gears.

Vessels operating with bottom trawls or seines with cod-end mesh sizes of 70-100mm in Division 6a with catches comprising more than 5% Norway lobster are able to claim the high survivability exemption for this species providing they use gears with one of; a 300 mm squared mesh panel (200 mm for vessels <12m), a Seltra panel, a sorting grid with 35 mm bar spacing, a Netgrid or a Flip-flap trawl.

4.7.3 Methods for Reducing Discards

This chapter report on the main recent initiatives in Scotland and in Denmark.

4.7.3.1 Scotland

In Scotland a cooperative body, the Gear Innovation and Technology Advisory Group (GITAG) was established in August 2015. GITAG is an industry-based body with Marine Scotland participation, and is hosted by the Scottish Fishermen's Federation (SFF). GITAG aims to foster flexible

partnerships between active fishermen, industry and public bodies, gear technologists and science; aimed at trialling innovations to existing gear categories, piloting new gear configurations and types with associated data collection and appropriate scientific analysis, in order to support the full implementation of the Landings Obligation. The Group is also responsible for industry-wide dissemination of project-related knowledge, research results and best practice, recommending a suite of evaluated gears. GITAG is 100% grant funded under the EMFF programme.

GITAG has carried out and disseminated six gear design modification trials, as detailed below:

Gear	Target Species	Objective	Area	Link
Coverless trawl with square mesh panels	Norway lobster	Reduce unwanted catches of haddock and whiting	ICES Div. 4a-b	https://www.sff.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/GITAG-Aurelia-Jun18.pdf
Inclined netting panel and double cod-ends	Norway lobster	Demonstrate possibility of separating fish and <i>Nephrops</i> within the gear	ICES Div. 4a-b	https://www.sff.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/GITAG-Amity-Jun18.pdf
Square mesh escape panels	Norway lobster	Cod avoidance	ICES Div 4a-b	https://www.sff.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/GITAG-Atlas-Jun18.pdf
Ground gear modification	Mixed Norway lobster and demersal fish	Reduced bycatch of round and flatfish	ICES SA 4	https://www.sff.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/GITAG-Zenith-Jul18.pdf
Four panel cod-end	Whitefish	Reduced undersized bycatch	ICES SA 4	https://www.sff.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/GITAG-Ocean-Harvest-Harvester.pdf
Inclined netting panel and double cod-ends (phase II)	Norway lobster	Further develop the selectivity aspect of the Amity Selector Panel Trawl	ICES Div 4b (Nephrops FU 6)	https://www.sff.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/GITAG-Amity-Phase2-Jul18.pdf

4.7.3.2 Denmark

Denmark has experimented with fully documented fisheries and electronic monitoring since 2008. The main initiative related to discard reduction and adaptation to the landing obligation has been the partly EMFF-funded project on Cod Catch Quota Management trial, running from 2010 to 2016. The project was a collaboration between DTU Aqua and the Danish Fisheries Agency. The

project tested the possibility for fishers to obtain low discard ratios by complying to Catch Quota rather than Landings Quota Management. That is, fishers were required to enter discards in the electronic logbook and these would count against the TAC of the vessel. In order to verify the entries, electronic monitoring with video was installed on participating vessels. The initial project preceded the introduction of the landing obligation as the first run of the project began in 2010. Vessels were given additional quota of cod and exemptions from days-at-sea regulation for participation. The original scope of the project aimed at testing Catch Quota Management solely for cod and the feasibility of electronic monitoring with video as a means to verify fishermen's self-reported entries. However, with the introduction of the landing obligation the project objectives were adapted, adding whiting, hake, haddock and saithe to the video audit. Participating vessels proved to have low discard ratios (< 5%) in general for audited species when adapting their fishing strategies to reduce discards of cod.

The project was finished in April 2017¹. The number of participating vessels varied with lowest at 7 in 2010 to the highest being 24 in 2016. 12 vessels participated in the last year of the project. Vessels were mainly demersal trawlers, although three gillnetters and four Danish seiners also participated in the project during the years. Three demersal trawlers participated in all years of the project. All vessels had their main fishing grounds in the North Sea and Skagerrak.

Based on these experiences, another project called MINIDISC was initiated in 2014. It aimed at letting voluntary fishers experiment with discards reduction strategies under fully documented fisheries conditions, in a "challenge experiment" frame. 12 vessels participated in the Baltic Sea, North Sea and Skagerrak, with contrasted results. The trials were funded by the EMFF, but the full analysis of the results was completed during DiscardLess, and reported in Deliverable D4.3 and in Mortensen et al. (2017a,b;2018)

These experiences led to another EMFF-funded, industry lead initiative in Denmark in 2017. This project called FastTrack (www.fast-track.dk) aims to speed up the process from conceptualisation of problems with catch composition to delivery of a gear-based solution that can be rolled out by the industry (Eliassen et al., 2018). It is a collaboration between DTU Aqua, Aalborg University, and the Danish Fish Producers Organisation. The project provides fishers with the possibility to test the gears they feel best suit their fishery and quota allocation. The project pays for the development of the gear, and if it appears to offer a successful solution, a full scientific documentation is carried out using a chartered vessel and scientific quota. This provides an evidence base to demonstrate the utility of any change to other fishers, promoting industry-wide take up of more selective gears, as well as to managers and policy-makers, who would need to be involved in any legislative changes required.

The project was finished in March 2019¹³. 13 vessels were involved in the project where a total of 19 gears were developed and tested. All gears developed pertained to the demersal trawl fisheries,

¹³ FAST TRACK - Sustainable, cost effective and responsive gear solutions under the landing obligation. Jordan P Feekings, Rikke P Frandsen, Ludvig Krag, Henrik Lund, Tiago Veiga-Malta, Søren Qvist Eliassen, Rikke Becker Jacobsen, Hanne Bohnstedt, Valentina Melli, Marco Nalon, Lars O Mortensen, Clara Ulrich, Mollie Brooks. DTU Aqua.

namely the Baltic Sea cod trawl fishery, *Pandalus* trawl fishery, Nephrops trawl fishery, and the Brown shrimp beam trawl fishery. The gears tested either aimed at reducing catches of unwanted species and/or sizes. Of the 19 gears developed, 4 were taken through to scientific testing, and 2 of these presented to managers for possible implementation in regulations.

Issues investigated by the Danish Fast-Track project.

Fishery	Problem	solution	Vessel number
<i>Nephrops</i> trawl fishery	Bycatch of fish	Grid, divided codend, scaring devices, scaring lines	FN459, HG398, ND58, O91, FN436
Baltic cod fishery	Bycatch of small cod / loss of legal sized cod	Mesh size, lastridge ropes, circumference	R218, R222, R3
Baltic cod fishery	Bycatch of flounder	Grid	R200, R3
<i>Pandalus</i> trawl fishery	Bycatch of small shrimp	T90 codend, size sorting grid, square mesh panel	S486
Brown shrimp beam trawl fishery	Bycatch of fish	Grid	L299
Brown shrimp beam trawl fishery	Bycatch of small shrimp	Size sorting grid	E426

In total, the results from approximately half of the gears developed were as intended, while one (PAN-1) was deemed not as intended. Approximately half of the trials gave unclear results and was primarily due to the need for more data. Of the 19 gears developed, the majority (13) are not permitted to be used in the fisheries and require management action, 5 of the gears developed are already permitted to be used, while one requires management action to facilitate its uptake. Of the 13 gears developed which are not permitted to be used, 7 are not permitted due to the need for more data, while 4 have/are to be presented to managers. For 2 of the gears tested (COD-1 and COD-2), there are no plans to present them to managers as they were developed to help understand the effects of specific design changes.

Table 3. Summary of the different individual trials carried out during the Fast-Track project.

Vessel	Gear	Target species	Main topic	Project	Results	Uptake by industry	Factsheet
R 218 Judith Bechmann	Baltic cod trawl	Cod	Size selectivity cod	Improved selectivity in T90 codends in the Baltic cod fishery - Phase I	Green	Red	COD-1-3
R 222 Børnø	Baltic cod trawl	Cod	Size selectivity cod	Improved selectivity in T90 codends in the Baltic cod fishery - Phase II	Yellow	Red	COD-4
R 3 Orion	Baltic cod trawl	Cod	Size selectivity cod	Improved selectivity in T90 codends in the Baltic cod fishery - Phase II	Green	Red	COD-5
R 200 Cometen	Baltic cod trawl	Cod	Species selectivity flounder	Species sorting grid to reduce catches of flounder	* Yellow	Red	COD-6
R 3 Orion	Baltic cod trawl	Cod	Species selectivity flounder	Species sorting grid to reduce catches of flounder	* Yellow	Red	COD-7-8
S 486 Sajoni	Pandalus trawl	Pandalus	Size selectivity pandalus	Size selective sorting grid to reduce catches of small Pandalus	Red	Green	PAN-1
S 486 Sajoni	Pandalus trawl	Pandalus	Size selectivity pandalus	T90 codend and square mesh panel to reduce catches of small Pandalus	* Yellow	Green	PAN-2-3
S 84 Ida-Katrine	Nephrops trawl	Nephrops	Species selectivity fish bycatch	Species sorting grid and dividend codend to reduce fish bycatch	* Yellow	Red	NEP-1
FN 459 M Jerup	Nephrops trawl	Nephrops	Species selectivity fish bycatch	A modified Seltra panel & behaviour stimulators to reduce fish bycatch	* Green	Green	NEP-2
HG 398 Nitrime	Nephrops trawl	Nephrops	Species selectivity fish bycatch	Species sorting grid and dividend codend to reduce fish bycatch	* Green	Red	NEP-3
ND 58 Moonlight	Nephrops trawl	Nephrops	Species selectivity fish bycatch	Divided codend to reduce fish bycatch	* Yellow	Red	NEP-4
O 91 Albatros	Nephrops trawl	Nephrops	Increase catch rates Nephrops	Real-time catch sensor to increase catch rates and reduce fish bycatch	* Green	Green	NEP-5
FN 436 Tove Kajgaard	Nephrops trawl	Nephrops	Species selectivity fish bycatch	Scaring lines ahead of the trawl to reduce fish bycatch	Green	Yellow	NEP-6
L 299 Mallebukken	Beam trawl	Brown shrimp	Species selectivity fish bycatch	Species sorting grid as an alternative to a seive net	* Yellow	Red	CRAN-1
E 426 Rune Egholm	Beam trawl	Brown shrimp	Size selectivity Brown shrimp	Size selective sorting grid to reduce catches of small Brown shrimp	Green	Red	CRAN-2

Results as intended	Green	Green	Already in use, no further actions needed
Unclear results, further development needed	Yellow	Yellow	Permitted, incentive needed
Results not as intended	Red	Red	Not permitted, management action needed
more data needed *			

For beam trawl fisheries, much recent work on the selectivity has been focussed on issues surrounding the use of electric pulse trawls, which result in increased performance of the gear but have unknown effects on selectivity. Work on incorporating selectivity measures has been carried out in the Netherlands and Belgium, looking at their beam trawl sole fisheries. These operate with an 80 mm cod end, which also keeps undersized plaice, dab and other demersal species. Various separation- and escape panels have been tested in the beam trawl, pulse trawl and pulse wing gears.

The most promising results were achieved with a separation panel in combination with an escape panel. The separation panel was aimed to guide all the fish that are located higher up in the net to the upper side of the net, where the undersized fish can escape through a square mesh panel of 160 or 200 millimetres. The other fish ends up in the cod end. The assumption with this construction is that sole swims underneath the separation panel into the cod end. With this net adaptation, 30 per cent less flatfish discards were caught during test journeys, but also 9 per cent less market sized sole. Further trials have been conducted with an electric Benthos Release Panel (eBRP) - a panel with square meshes at the bottom of the net, through which benthos can fall before it enters the cod end – and with the addition of a light weight ground rope ahead of the conventional rope and ahead of the pulse electrodes as well as a separation panel that guides the fish over the electrodes to the upper side of the net. The upper side has wider meshes through which undersized plaice and dab can escape. The assumption behind this construction is that a separation can be made between sole and other flat fish in front of the electric pulse field.

Some description of these results can be found in the “Best Practices I and II” projects ¹⁴ and STECF PLEN 18-03 report¹⁵ summarising the road map for plaice in the landing obligation

A gear design which has been trialed and developed in southern North Sea *Nephrops* fisheries is the SepNep net. Various net designs have been tested the past years in order to lose discards in the *Nephrops* fishery. This was developed during 2016 by an international cooperation between the German Thünen Institute, Wageningen Marine Research, the Dutch Ministry of Economic Affairs and the Nederlandse Visserbond. This is a multi cod-end gear which uses a separation panel to guide fish into an upper cod end, which has wide meshes and a square-mesh panel allowing undersized fish to escape. *Nephrops* pass through this separation panel where they encounter a sorting grid at the entrance of the lower cod end. Small *Nephrops* can escape through the grid while larger individuals are guided into a middle cod end. During trials, a third cod end was attached behind the sorting grid in order to retain the small *Nephrops*, however when this net is used in practice the lowest cod end is removed allowing these individuals to escape the net freely. This net design is now specified in the North Sea discard reduction plan.

4.7.4 Changes in the data collection and processing

Discard data are collected at sea by on board sampling programmes funded by the Data Collection Framework (EC, 199/2008). For sampling purposes, only the major metiers are considered, which are selected using a ranking system. Only those metiers whose accumulated shares in landings, value and effort are included in the top 90% are selected. For this reason, the metiers sampled can change with the years.

Information on discards is used as inputs in the stock assessments of the main target species carried out annually by ICES.

The trip-level sampling coverage by nation in the North Sea for each main metier is summarized in annual reports, available from the DG Maritime Affairs website in annual summary spreadsheets. (<https://datacollection.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ars>). Changes in the way data has been aggregated between metiers across years and countries mean that summarising the data is challenging, however sampling figures for selected metiers are presented below.

Country	Metier	Year	Trips	No. Sampled	% Coverage
Belgium	TBB_DEF	2013	1328	25	
		2014	1941	18	
		2015	1758	20	

¹⁴ <http://www.europarl.europa.eu/cmsdata/161030/Presentation%20by%20Pim%20Visser,%20VisNed%20-%20EAPO,%20the%20Netherlands.pdf>

¹⁵ <https://stecf.jrc.ec.europa.eu/reports/plenary>

		2016	1607	26	
		2017	1675	31	
Denmark	GNS_DEF	2013	4110	55	
		2014			
		2015			
		2016	4382	15	
		2017			
	OTB_MCD	2013	15382	104	
		2014	15487	122	
		2015			
		2016	17053	124	
		2017			
	SDN_DEF	2013	1682	12	
		2014	2551	12	
		2015			
		2016	1664	4	
		2017			
	TBB_CRU	2013	1924	10	
		2014	2303	12	
		2015			
		2016	2273	16	
		2017			

4.7.5 Changes in discards volumes and fish stocks

Cod

North Sea cod is an iconic species and its status is often seen as a bellwether of the health of northern European seas. Stocks reached historically low levels in 2006. Various schemes were implemented in an effort to restore the stock through catch avoidance, incentivising vessels to use more selective gears and move away from areas where cod were found. The ability to incentivise fishers in this way was superseded by the implementation of the Landings Obligation in 2016. ICES estimates of discard rates have fallen from an average of 28% over 2005 – 2015, driven primarily by high discarding in 2007 and 2008, to an average of 22% in 2016 – 2017 (Figure 18). The latest assessment shows the 2015 year class to be the strongest recruitment seen this century, and these efforts to reduce discarding may be integral to reduced mortality on these fish before they enter the fished component of the stock.

Figure 18. ICES estimates of landings and discards of North Sea cod, 2005 - 2017.

Haddock

Haddock in the North Sea is known to produce highly variable and unpredictable pulses of large recruitment which sustain the stock and fishery for several years. The most notable recent example was the 1999 year-class, which formed the major part of the stock through the early part of the 21st century. These pulses of recruitment are often heavily discarded in their first years before they grow to a marketable size, however recruitment in recent years has been poor, therefore it is likely that the full implications of the Landings Obligation for this stock have not yet been felt. Discard rates have declined from an average of 23% over the period 2005 -2015, to 16% after the implementation of the landings obligation.

Figure 19. ICES estimates of landings and discards of North Sea and West of Scotland haddock, 2005 - 2017.

Saithe

Discards of saithe make up a relatively small proportion of catches, both in the North Sea and to the west of Scotland. Although discards in the North Sea appear to have increased following the implementation of the Landings Obligation, from 8% to 12%, this appears to be noise driven by a high value of 14.6% in 2016 (Figure 20). Discards to the west of Scotland appear to have declined steeply, from 12% to 2% of catches, although the data in this time series appears to be more variable (Figure 21).

Figure 20. ICES estimates of landings and discards of North Sea saithe, 2005 - 2017.

Figure 21. ICES estimates of landings and discards of West of Scotland Saithe, 2005 - 2017.

Whiting

Whiting are a species which has historically been heavily discarded, and there is no evidence that the implementation of the landings obligation has changed this situation, with average discard rates prior to its introduction of 38%, increasing to 46% in 2016 and 2017 (Figure 22).

Figure 22. ICES estimates of landings and discards of North Sea whiting, 2005 - 2017.

Sole

As a high value species, discards of sole have always been relatively low. Following the implementation of the landings obligation, discard rates have fallen from 11% to 8% (Figure 23).

Figure 23. ICES estimates of landings and discards of North Sea sole, 2005 - 2017.

Plaice

Discard rates of plaice in the North Sea have historically been at a high level, with the species being taken as a bycatch in directed sole, *Nephrops* and whitefish fisheries. The stock size has increased to unprecedented levels, with a spawning stock biomass of just under 1m tonnes, however catches and discard rates have remained relatively stable in recent years (Figure 24).

Figure 24. ICES estimates of landings and discards of North Sea plaice, 2005 - 2017.

Hake

Discrete catch and discard data for hake in the North Sea and West of Scotland is only available from 2013 onwards. The picture is one of increasing catches and discards which have remained relatively constant in terms of volume, and therefore declining discard rates falling from 17% to 9% following the implementation of the Landings Obligation in 2016 (Figure 25).

Figure 25. ICES estimates of landings and discards of Hake in Subareas 3, 4 and 6, 2005 - 2017.

Norway Lobster

Nephrops are assessed and advised upon on the basis of individual „functional units“ – areas of muddy seabed which form discrete patches of suitable habitat for *Nephrops* burrows. While management takes place at the ICES Subarea level. Discard rates are therefore available on a relatively fine spatial scale, and which reflect the variable nature of *Nephrops* vital rates, fisheries and stock dynamics. *Nephrops* became subject to the landings obligation in 2016 on both the west coast of Scotland and in the North Sea, and, noting the short time series of post-implementation data, discard rates have declined across all functional units in the case study area following the introduction of the Landings Obligation. Catches in the North Sea are dominated by the Fladen, which peaked in 2009 and declined strongly thereafter, due to economic factors rather than stock status. Discards of *Nephrops* fell to near zero in 2011 and have remained at very low levels since then (Figure 26). Catches from the other smaller functional units show a mixed picture of success, with average discard rates around 19% both before and after the implementation of the Landings

Obligation (Figure 27), while falling from 19% (2005 – 2015) to 9% (2016 – 2017) in the Firth of Forth (Figure 28) and 5% to 4% over the same period in the Moray Firth (Figure 29).

Figure 26. Nephrops landings and discards from Subarea 4, Functional Unit 7 (Fladen).

Figure 27. Nephrops landings and discards from Subarea 4, Functional Unit 6 (Farn Deep)

Figure 28. *Nephrops* landings and discards from Subarea 4, Functional Unit 8 (Firth of Forth)

Figure 29. *Nephrops* landings and discards from Subarea 4, Functional Unit 9 (Moray Firth)

On the west coast of Scotland, the three functional units all fall within 12 nautical miles of the Scottish coast and are therefore subject to specific measures relating to the use of highly selective gears. Again, the landings obligation was introduced in 2016 for these stocks, and average discard rates for the periods 2005 – 2015 and 2016 – 2017 were 7% and 4% for the North Minch (Figure 30), 6% and 5% for the South Minch (Figure 31) and 14% and 7% for the Clyde (Figure 32).

Figure 30. *Nephrops* landings and discards from Subarea 4, Functional Unit 11 (North Minch)

Figure 31. *Nephrops* landings and discards from Subarea 4, Functional Unit 12 (South Minch)

Figure 32. *Nephrops* landings and discards from Subarea 4, Functional Unit 13 (Clyde)

4.7.6 Changes in sensitive components of the ecosystem

No studies looking at the effects of the landings obligation on sensitive ecosystem components and VME indicator species have yet been carried out for the North Sea and waters to the west of Scotland.

4.8 Thermaikos Gulf Case Study (Eastern Mediterranean)

4.8.1 Introduction

The Eastern Mediterranean Northwestern (NW) Aegean includes the Gulfs of Thessaloniki (also known as inner Thermaikos) and Thermaikos as well as the gulfs of Chalkidiki Peninsula. Thermaikos Gulf is the main fishing ground, which is considered one of the most productive in the Greek Seas. Thermaikos Gulf is a shallow water area having a maximum depth of 50 m (Figure 33). Large river systems (Gallicos, Axios, Loudias and Aliakmon) discharge into Thermaikos Gulf about 207m³/s, with significant temporal variability (Kallianiotis et al. 2004).

Figure 33: Map of the Mediterranean Sea showing the GSAs (GSA 22: Aegean Sea), northern Aegean Sea and Thermaikos Gulf (case study area) with seabed bathymetry.

According to the Fleet Register (KAM 2014), in 2014, 1460 vessels were registered in 7 ports of Thermaikos Gulf (Thessaloniki: 739 vessels; Skala Katerinis: 251 vessels; Nea Moudania: 232 vessels; Nea Michaniona: 82 vessels; Platamonas: 71 vessels; Agiokampos: 66 vessels; Stomio: 19 vessels). Based on the main gear used, 58 of these vessels are trawlers (using bottom trawls, OTB), 29 are purse seiners (using purse-seines, PS) and 1373 are small-scale coastal vessels using a variety of fishing gears. The percentage of active vessels to the total will be determined within the framework of this project.

Following Thracian Sea, Thermaikos Gulf concentrates the second highest fishing effort of trawlers in the Aegean Sea (GSA 22). In total, 47.6% of trawling in the Aegean takes place in

Thermaikos Gulf and Thracian Sea. As far as purse-seiners are concerned, 20.23% of purse-seining in the Aegean Sea (GSA 22) takes place in Thermaikos Gulf.

4.8.1.1 Causes of discarding

All métiers used in Thermaikos Gulf share the same market and regulation causes for discarding. The general fisheries regulations for the Greek seas, based on the European legislation, apply in Thermaikos Gulf. For example, Minimum Landing Size (MLS) is the main reason for discarding hake *Merluccius merluccius*, red mullet *Mullus barbatus* and cuttlefish *Sepia spp.*, while low market demand is the reason of discarding spottail mantis shrimp *Squilla mantis* and other crustaceans. Discarding practices are influenced by fishing processes and fishers' decision making, which, at least in Greek waters, is affected by several factors, including weather conditions, economic pressure, market demands, fishing strategies, skipper's knowledge and skills (Tsitsika and Maravelias 2006).

Based on the classification by Eliassen and Christensen (2012), the factors affecting discards in the Mediterranean may be divided into four categories: (a) natural conditions including species composition and abundance, resource availability, species invasions, and environmental factors (depth, seabed, productivity); (b) community (haul duration, sorting practices, soak time); (c) states and regulations that include technical measures (gear selectivity), spatiotemporal closures, MLS, control mechanisms; and (d) market influence including economic value of species (damaged, unwanted catch), resource use related to socio-economic factors, storage capacity of the vessel and sorting capacity of the crew (Eliassen and Christensen 2012). These factors often act in synergistic manner that may not be straightforward to disentangle, especially in multispecies fisheries, which is the case in the Mediterranean (Tsagarakis et al. 2014). As a result, high regional, seasonal, and interannual fluctuations are observed even for one given fishing gear (Tsagarakis et al. 2014).

4.8.1.2 Effects of discarding

The survival rates of discards have not been evaluated in the northern Aegean Sea. With the exception of some species, survivability is considered to be very low in the area. There is a study on the survival rates of three fish species, the brown comber (*Serranus hepatus*), black goby (*Gobius niger*) and annular seabream (*Diplodus annularis*), after their escape from a 40 mm stretched diamond mesh polyethylene (PE) codend that has been conducted in eastern Aegean Sea (Duzbastilar et al. 2010). With very short (15 in duration) hauls, the mean survival mean survival percentages of open codend and experimental cages were found to be 97.1% and 98.3% for brown comber, 69.0% and 77.2% for black goby, and 97.5% and 98.6% for annular seabream respectively. The "Choke effect" is not applicable in any of Thermaikos Gulf fisheries because, contrary to several north Atlantic fisheries, there are no quota restrictions in the study area.

Although the ecological effects of discards have not yet been evaluated in Thermaikos Gulf, the cascading effect across the marine food web is expected to be high (e.g. seabirds: Arcos and Oro 2002) at all level of biological organization (Sarda et al. 2015). Data on the effect of purse-seine discards exists only for Thracian Sea (Tsagarakis et al. 2012), while the general effects of discards have been recently reviewed (Tsagarakis et al. 2014). The potential impacts of discard landing

obligation may be dramatic for the Mediterranean Sea, where a large part of discards is already composed of juvenile fishes with body sizes smaller than the minimum landing sizes and of invertebrates (Sarda et al. 2015).

The economic, operational and technical costs associated with the manipulation and storage of discards on board may be high (Sarda et al. 2015). These costs may include additional crew and storage costs and landings costs (boxes, storage, ice). The monitoring and controlling costs to prevent fishers from discarding when at sea are also expected to be high (Sarda et al. 2015).

4.8.2 Adopted discard plan for the region

In the Eastern Mediterranean, the following Regulations apply:

5.2.1. Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 1392/2014 of 20 October 2014 establishing a discard plan for certain small pelagic fisheries in the Mediterranean Sea.

This Regulation specified the details for implementing the landing obligation in the Mediterranean Sea, to all catches of species which are subject to minimum sizes in small pelagic fisheries. Article No. 3 sets out the “*de minimis*” exemption, which specifies the quantities that may be discarded in the different Mediterranean areas of the General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean (GFCM) Geographical Sub-Areas (GSAs). That includes the Aegean Sea (GSA 22), the Ionian Sea (GSA 20) and Crete Island (GSA 23). The regulation applied from 1 January 2015 until 31 December 2017.

5.2.2. COMMISSION DELEGATED REGULATION (EU) 2018/161 of 23 October 2017 establishing a *de minimis* exemption to the landing obligation for certain small pelagic fisheries in the Mediterranean Sea

This Regulation aims to progressively eliminate discards in all Union fisheries through the introduction of a landing obligation for catches of species subject to catch limits or minimum sizes. In the small pelagic mid-water trawl and purse seines fisheries set out in the Western Mediterranean Sea, small pelagic fisheries in the South Eastern Mediterranean Sea (GFCM Geographical Sub-Areas (GSA) 15, 16, 19, 20, 22 23 and 25 for mid-water pelagic trawls and GFCM GSA 25 for purse seines targeting anchovy, sardine, mackerel and horse mackerel) and small pelagic fisheries in the Adriatic Sea, up to 5 % of the total annual catches of any species subject to a minimum size may be discarded. In the small pelagic purse seines fisheries of small pelagic fisheries in the Malta Island and South of Sicily, small pelagic fisheries in the Aegean Sea and Crete Island (GFCM GSAs 22 and 23 for purse seines targeting anchovy, sardine, mackerel and horse mackerel) and small pelagic fisheries in the Southern Adriatic and Ionian Sea (GFCM GSAs 18, 19 and 20 for purse seines targeting anchovy, sardine, mackerel and horse mackerel), up to 3 % of the total annual catches of any species subject to a minimum size may be discarded. This Regulation has entered into force on 1st January 2018 and shall apply until 31st December 2020. Paragraphs 1 and 2 of the Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2018/161 of 23 October 2017 shall apply by way of derogation from Article 15(1) of Regulation (EU) No 1380/2013.

5.2.3. Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2017/86 of 20 October 2016 establishing a discard plan for certain demersal fisheries in the Mediterranean Sea

In the Mediterranean Sea, as of 1 January 2017 the landing obligation will be compulsory for demersal species that define the fisheries and that are subject to a minimum conservation reference size as defined in the "Mediterranean Regulation (Annex III to Regulation (EC) No 1967/2006). The fisheries targeting hake, red mullet, common sole and deep water rose shrimp in certain areas of the Mediterranean Sea are subject to this provision. This regulation shall apply from 1st January 2017 until 31st December 2019. The new plan establishes detailed rules for the implementation of the landing obligation in these fisheries, including different levels of "*de minimis*" exemptions depending on the area and fishing gear used. Under this exemption, operators can discard a small percentage of unwanted catches, given that the costs of their handling would be disproportionate.

The plan also stipulates a number of survivability exemptions, allowing operators to throw back specimen that have a high chance of surviving (for example for sole caught with beam trawls and for scallop, carpet clams and venus shells caught with mechanized dredges). The survivability exemptions are delivered for one year, and Member States are to provide additional scientific data in the course of 2017 for possible renewal.

These exceptions were examined by the EU's scientific advisory body, i.e. the Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries (STECF). All the provisions of the discard plan stem from the joint recommendations drawn up by the Member States concerned namely Greece, Spain, France, Croatia, Italy, Cyprus, Malta and Slovenia, after consultation of the Mediterranean Sea Advisory Council (MEDAC).

4.8.3 Methods for reducing discard

In Greece, the national institute HCMR has carried out the gear selectivity project EPILEXIS (see <http://epilexis.hcmr.gr/>) in the Aegean Sea. The project compared 3 types of the trawl codend (40 mm diamond, 40mm square and 50mm diamond) and made selectivity studies for the 5 most commercial species.

The results show that square mesh size has the better selectivity and reduces discards. In most cases, commercial catch was not significantly altered. The ratio of discards/commercial catch was reduced from 0.57 (40D), to 0.49 (40S) and 0.51 (50D). Square mesh size of 40S had the best selectivity curve, shifted to larger lengths and larger L50. Diamond 40D mesh size has the lower selectivity, Diamond 50D mesh size withholds more young fish compared to 40S and allows escapees of larger size, especially for striped red mullet. The square 40S mesh size allows a significant part of young hake to escape. Despite that, the largest part of the hake catch is below the minimum landing size of 20 cm in the codend.

4.8.4 Changes in the data collection and processing

The most reliable source of information for Greece is the fisheries data collection scheme under data collection regulation / data collection framework (DCR/DCF) (EU 2000, 2008), but these EU regulations have only been implemented sporadically (from 2003 to 2006, 2008 and 2014).

The Data Collection Programme for Greece is carried out by two partners, the Hellenic Agricultural Organization – Demeter (ELGO-DEMETER) that is the project’s Scientific Co-ordinator and the Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (H.C.M.R.). Two institutes from each partner contribute to the realization of the NP. Specifically, from the ELGO-DEMETER participates the Fisheries Research Institute (F.R.I) and the Agricultural Economics Research Institute (AGR.E.R.I). The FRI is a semi state marine research organisation responsible for collection of scientific data on the fisheries sector in North and Central Aegean Sea, on eel and on processing industry. The AGR.E.R.I is also a semi state research organisation responsible for collection and evaluation of economic data on the fisheries sector. From H.C.M.R participates the Institute of Marine Biological Resources & Inland Waters of Athens (I.M.B.R-Athens) and the Institute of Marine Biological Resources of Crete (I.M.B.R-Crete). The I.M.B.R is a semi state marine research organisation responsible for the collection of scientific data on the fisheries sector in South Aegean Sea, Ionian Sea and Cretan Sea. It also has the management of the database and GIS Fisheries Information System called IMAS-Fish which supports the Data Collection programme.

Discarding rates of commercially exploited species are calculated from metier based discard sampling carried out as part of the concurrent sampling at sea programme. Trip specific discard rates by species in weight are raised to discard rates by quarter and metier using species landings data.

4.8.5 Changes in discards volumes and fish stocks

For Greece, the most recent data are the ones from the Data Collection Framework (DCF) programme for 2015. The official discards data for 2016 and after are not available because the biological sampling within the framework of DCF in Greece was not properly executed in some years. In addition, the official landings collection scheme from the Hellenic Statistical Authorities changed in 2016 and onwards making the two datasets not comparable. The latest reliable discard dataset is the one reported in Table 1 below.

Table 16: Discard data for Greece from the Data Collection Framework programme for the year 2015. The ratio Rd/c is the ratio of discards (d) to the total catch (c), the 95% confidence level of the estimate CI and the relative estimation errors ER at the 95% confidence level per fishing gear and GFCM Geographical Sub-Area. **GSA-20: Eastern Ionian Sea**, **GSA-22: Aegean Sea (includes Case study area)**, **GSA-23: Crete**. Species with bold characters are the ones included in Annex III ("undersized marine organisms") of Council Regulation (EC) No 1967/2006 of 21 December 2006.

Fishing gear	Area	Species	Rd/c	CI	RE
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Aspitrigla cuculus</i>	0.68	0.13	0.19
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Boops boops</i>	0.32	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Citharus linguatula</i>	0.82	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Diplodus annularis</i>	1.00	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Engraulis encrasicolus</i>	1.00	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Eutrigla gurnardus</i>	0.16	0.01	0.03

OTB	GSA-20	<i>Galeus melastomus</i>	0.85	0.13	0.15
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Helicolenus dactylopterus</i>	0.44	0.09	0.21
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Lepidorhombus boscii</i>	0.18	0.28	1.61
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Lophius budegassa</i>	0.05	0.00	0.09
OTB	GSA-20	Merluccius merluccius	0.03	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Micromesistius poutassou</i>	0.00	0.00	0.39
OTB	GSA-20	Mullus barbatus	0.02	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-20	Mullus surmuletus	0.06	0.01	0.22
OTB	GSA-20	Pagellus acarne	0.81	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-20	Pagellus bogaraveo	1.00	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-20	Pagellus erythrinus	0.09	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Phycis blennoides</i>	0.22	0.08	0.36
OTB	GSA-20	Sardina pilchardus	0.98	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Sardinella aurita</i>	1.00	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-20	Scomber colias	0.09	0.01	0.08
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	0.53	0.49	0.92
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Trigla lucerna</i>	0.13	0.00	0.03
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Loligo vulgaris</i>	0.00	0.00	0.03
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Aspitrigla cuculus</i>	0.29	0.01	0.02
OTB	GSA-22	Engraulis encrasicolus	1.00	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Galeus melastomus</i>	0.99	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Micromesistius poutassou</i>	0.07	0.00	0.03
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Raja clavata</i>	0.01	0.00	0.07
OTB	GSA-22	Solea solea	0.00	0.00	0.05
OTB	GSA-22	Trachurus trachurus	0.69	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Eledone moschata</i>	0.03	0.00	0.05
OTB	GSA-22	Parapenaeus longirostris	0.15	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Helicolenus dactylopterus</i>	1.00	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-23	Merluccius merluccius	0.13	0.00	0.02
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Raja clavata</i>	0.30	0.41	1.37
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Trigla lucerna</i>	0.35	0.06	0.18
OTB	GSA-20	Solea solea	0.01	0.00	0.05
OTB	GSA-20	Sparus aurata	0.19	0.01	0.03
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Spicara smaris</i>	0.89	0.03	0.04
OTB	GSA-20	Trachurus mediterraneus	0.65	0.01	0.02
OTB	GSA-20	Trachurus trachurus	0.69	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Trigloporus lastoviza</i>	0.07	0.00	0.05
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Trisopterus minutus</i>	0.09	0.00	0.03
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Zeusfaber</i>	0.09	0.00	0.04
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Sepia officinalis</i>	0.03	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Illex coindetii</i>	0.03	0.00	0.12
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Eledone spp</i>	0.08	0.00	0.02
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Squilla mantis</i>	0.64	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-20	Trachurus spp	0.50	0.49	0.98
OTB	GSA-20	Parapenaeus longirostris	0.09	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Melicertus kerathurus</i>	0.01	0.00	0.02

OTB	GSA-22	<i>Boops boops</i>	0.30	0.01	0.03
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Citharus linguatula</i>	0.55	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Diplodus annularis</i>	0.63	0.04	0.07
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Diplodus vulgaris</i>	0.13	0.06	0.46
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Eutrigla gurnardus</i>	0.37	0.01	0.04
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Helicolenus dactylopterus</i>	0.25	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Lepidorhombus boscii</i>	0.22	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Lophius budegassa</i>	0.03	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Lophius piscatorius</i>	0.03	0.00	0.09
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Merluccius merluccius</i>	0.04	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Mullus barbatus</i>	0.01	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Pagellus acarne</i>	0.76	0.01	0.01
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Pagellus bogaraveo</i>	0.66	0.01	0.01
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Pagellus erythrinus</i>	0.15	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Phycis blennoides</i>	0.23	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>	0.98	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Sardinella aurita</i>	0.23	0.04	0.16
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Scomber colias</i>	0.52	0.01	0.02
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Scomber scombrus</i>	0.03	0.00	0.06
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	0.25	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Sparus aurata</i>	0.15	0.14	0.92
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Spicara maena</i>	0.90	0.09	0.10
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Spicara smarts</i>	0.18	0.01	0.07
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Squalus acantbias</i>	0.02	0.01	0.59
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Trachurus mediterraneus</i>	0.99	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Trigloporus lastoviza</i>	0.03	0.00	0.14
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Trisopterus minutus</i>	0.25	0.01	0.03
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Zeus faber</i>	0.04	0.00	0.02
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Sepia officinalis</i>	0.01	0.00	0.02
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Octopus vulgaris</i>	0.00	0.00	0.05
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Eidone cirrhosa</i>	0.03	0.02	0.58
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Loligo vulgaris</i>	0.01	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Illex coindetii</i>	0.04	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Squilla mantis</i>	0.08	0.00	0.02
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Nephrops norvegicus</i>	0.01	0.00	0.04
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Melicertus kerathurus</i>	0.00	0.00	0.03
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Aspitrigla cuculus</i>	0.55	0.03	0.05
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Boops boops</i>	0.02	0.00	0.03
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Citharus linguatula</i>	0.98	0.01	0.01
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Engraulis encrasicolus</i>	0.75	0.07	0.10
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Lophius budegassa</i>	0.03	0.00	0.14
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Mullus barbatus</i>	0.01	0.00	0.04
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Pagellus acarne</i>	0.96	0.01	0.01
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Pagellus erythrinus</i>	0.03	0.00	0.05
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Pagrus pagrus</i>	0.77	0.02	0.02
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Phycis blermoides</i>	0.54	0.07	0.13

OTB	GSA-23	<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>	0.35	0.08	0.23
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Scorpaena scrofa</i>	0.38	0.05	0.12
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	0.25	0.04	0.16
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Spicara smaris</i>	0.02	0.00	0.03
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	0.82	0.02	0.03
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Trigloporus lastoviza</i>	0.67	0.11	0.17
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Zeus faber</i>	0.00	0.00	0.29
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Eledone moschata</i>	0.00	0.00	0.09
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Illex coindetii</i>	0.07	0.01	0.08
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Parapenaeus longirostris</i>	0.03	0.00	0.09
PS	GSA-20	<i>Boops boops</i>	0.07	0.01	0.08
PS	GSA-20	<i>Citharus lingua tula</i>	1.00	0.00	0.00
PS	GSA-20	<i>Diplodus annularis</i>	0.82	0.03	0.04
PS	GSA-20	<i>Diplodus vulgaris</i>	0.53	0.12	0.24
PS	GSA-20	<i>Engraulis encrasicolus</i>	0.01	0.00	0.52
PS	GSA-20	<i>Mullus barbatus</i>	0.01	0.00	0.15
PS	GSA-20	<i>Mullus surmuletus</i>	0.03	0.01	0.29
PS	GSA-20	<i>Pagellus acarne</i>	0.56	0.48	0.87
PS	GSA-20	<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>	0.05	0.00	0.07
PS	GSA-20	<i>Sardinella aurita</i>	0.46	0.02	0.04
PS	GSA-20	<i>Scomber colias</i>	0.00	0.00	0.18
PS	GSA-20	<i>Trachurus mediterraneus</i>	0.55	0.07	0.13
PS	GSA-20	<i>Trigloporus lastoviza</i>	0.05	0.03	0.63
PS	GSA-22	<i>Boops boops</i>	0.00	0.00	0.55
PS	GSA-22	<i>Engraulis encrasicolus</i>	0.01	0.00	0.09
PS	GSA-22	<i>Mullus barbatus</i>	0.09	0.09	0.99
PS	GSA-22	<i>Pagellus erythrinus</i>	0.02	0.01	0.78
PS	GSA-22	<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>	0.01	0.00	0.06
PS	GSA-22	<i>Sardinella aurita</i>	0.01	0.00	0.18
PS	GSA-22	<i>Scomber colias</i>	0.06	0.01	0.09
PS	GSA-22	<i>Scomber scombrus</i>	0.17	0.02	0.14
PS	GSA-22	<i>Spicara smaris</i>	0.11	0.19	1.75
PS	GSA-22	<i>Trachurus mediterraneus</i>	0.00	0.00	0.30
PS	GSA-22	<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	0.91	0.02	0.03
PS	GSA-22	<i>Loligo vulgaris</i>	0.48	0.17	0.35
PS	GSA-22	<i>Illex coindetii</i>	0.14	0.03	0.19
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Aspitrigla cuculus</i>	0.02	0.00	0.10
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Boops boops</i>	0.02	0.01	0.36
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Citharus linguatula</i>	0.34	0.03	0.08
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Diplodus annularis</i>	0.56	0.10	0.19
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Engraulis encrasicolus</i>	1.00	0.00	0.00
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Eutrigla gurnardus</i>	0.06	0.07	1.18
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Merluccius merluccius</i>	0.10	0.01	0.08
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Mullus barbatus</i>	0.03	0.00	0.10
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Pagellus acarne</i>	0.27	0.13	0.49
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Pagellus erythrinus</i>	0.48	0.04	0.09

GNS	GSA-20	<i>Raja clavata</i>	0.20	0.04	0.19
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Sarda sarda</i>	0.09	0.02	0.25
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Sardinella aurita</i>	1.00	0.00	0.00
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Scomber colias</i>	0.03	0.01	0.15
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	1.00	0.00	0.00
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Solea solea</i>	0.04	0.02	0.40
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	0.19	0.02	0.11
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Trisopterus minutus</i>	0.05	0.03	0.70
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Sepia officinalis</i>	0.45	0.48	1.08
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Loligo vulgaris</i>	0.43	0.24	0.56
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Squilla mantis</i>	0.34	0.03	0.08
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Parapenaeus longirostris</i>	0.03	0.03	0.99
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Melicertus kerathurus</i>	0.03	0.02	0.65
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Boops boops</i>	0.01	0.00	0.07
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Citharus linguatula</i>	0.08	0.06	0.73
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Diplodus annularis</i>	0.12	0.02	0.19
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Diplodus vulgaris</i>	0.52	0.07	0.14
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Engraulis encrasicolus</i>	1.00	0.00	0.00
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Eutrigla gurnardus</i>	1.00	0.00	0.00
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Lophius budegassa</i>	0.01	0.00	0.57
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Merluccius merluccius</i>	0.01	0.00	0.19
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Mullus barbatus</i>	0.01	0.00	0.07
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Mullus surmuletus</i>	0.01	0.00	0.05
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Pagellus acarne</i>	0.86	0.02	0.02
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Pagellus bogaraveo</i>	0.01	0.01	1.05
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Pagellus erythrinus</i>	0.21	0.01	0.06
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>	0.42	0.16	0.38
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Sardinella aurita</i>	0.02	0.00	0.29
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Scomber colias</i>	0.04	0.03	0.68
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Trachurus mediterraneus</i>	0.13	0.04	0.29
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Illex coindetii</i>	0.35	0.22	0.63
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Sparus aurata</i>	0.05	0.03	0.61
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Spicara smaris</i>	0.00	0.00	0.29
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	0.12	0.01	0.12
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Trigloporus lastoviza</i>	0.16	0.04	0.24
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Trisopterus minutus</i>	0.32	0.09	0.28
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Sepia officinalis</i>	0.05	0.01	0.22
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Octopus vulgaris</i>	0.00	0.00	0.70
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Squilla mantis</i>	0.37	0.06	0.16
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Nephrops norvegicus</i>	0.02	0.01	0.64
GNS	GSA-23	<i>Diplodus annularis</i>	0.44	0.00	0.01
GNS	GSA-23	<i>Solea solea</i>	0.43	0.01	0.03
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Boops boops</i>	0.11	0.02	0.17
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Diplodus annularis</i>	0.19	0.01	0.04
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Diplodus vulgaris</i>	0.02	0.00	0.11
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Engraulis encrasicolus</i>	1.00	0.00	0.00

GTR	GSA-20	<i>Lophius budegassa</i>	0.02	0.01	0.57
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Merluccius merluccius</i>	0.09	0.09	1.02
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Mullus barbatus</i>	0.06	0.00	0.05
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Pagellus acarne</i>	0.76	0.03	0.04
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Pagellus bogaraveo</i>	1.00	0.00	0.00
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Pagellus erythrinus</i>	0.03	0.00	0.07
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Pagrus pagrus</i>	0.13	0.06	0.50
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>	0.43	0.11	0.25
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Sardinella aurita</i>	0.49	0.27	0.55
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Scorpaena scrofa</i>	0.14	0.03	0.20
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Solea solea</i>	0.00	0.00	0.14
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Sparus aurata</i>	0.00	0.00	0.12
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Loligo vulgaris</i>	0.02	0.01	0.39
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Squilla mantis</i>	0.81	0.02	0.03
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Boops boops</i>	0.07	0.00	0.04
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Citharus linguatula</i>	0.14	0.02	0.16
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Diplodus annularis</i>	0.22	0.01	0.03
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Diplodus sargus</i>	0.34	0.07	0.22
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Diplodus vulgaris</i>	0.05	0.00	0.02
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Eutrigla gurnardus</i>	0.41	0.24	0.60
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Lepidorhombus boscii</i>	0.01	0.00	0.06
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Lophius budegassa</i>	0.03	0.00	0.08
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Lophius piscatorius</i>	0.02	0.01	0.48
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Mullus surmuletus</i>	0.03	0.00	0.02
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Pagellus acarne</i>	0.11	0.01	0.06
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Pagellus bogaraveo</i>	0.11	0.19	1.75
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Pagellus erythrinus</i>	0.05	0.00	0.02
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Pagrus pagrus</i>	0.09	0.04	0.51
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Sardinella aurita</i>	0.11	0.04	0.38
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	0.01	0.01	0.64
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Octopus vulgaris</i>	0.02	0.00	0.04
GTR	GSA-23	<i>Mullus barbatus</i>	0.04	0.00	0.04
GTR	GSA-23	<i>Trigloporus lastoviza</i>	0.24	0.06	0.24
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Phycis blennoides</i>	0.04	0.01	0.32
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Sarda sarda</i>	0.04	0.04	0.82
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>	0.34	0.07	0.21
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Scomber scombrus</i>	0.59	0.47	0.80
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Scorpaena scrofa</i>	0.06	0.01	0.09
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	0.06	0.07	1.01
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Solea solea</i>	0.01	0.00	0.09
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Spicara maena</i>	0.02	0.00	0.07
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Trachurus mediterraneus</i>	0.25	0.08	0.32
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Trigloporus lastoviza</i>	0.11	0.02	0.23
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Trisopterus minutus</i>	0.45	0.25	0.56
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Zeus faber</i>	0.10	0.01	0.12
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Sepia officinalis</i>	0.00	0.00	0.04

GTR	GSA-22	<i>Eledone moschata</i>	0.42	0.10	0.24
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Squilla mantis</i>	0.01	0.00	0.20
GTR	GSA-23	<i>Boops boops</i>	0.22	0.01	0.06
GTR	GSA-23	<i>Diplodus annularis</i>	0.74	0.01	0.01
GTR	GSA-23	<i>Diplodus sargus</i>	0.11	0.04	0.34
GTR	GSA-23	<i>Diplodus vulgaris</i>	0.17	0.01	0.08
GTR	GSA-23	<i>Mullus surmuletus</i>	0.03	0.00	0.05
GTR	GSA-23	<i>Pagellus acarne</i>	0.29	0.02	0.06
GTR	GSA-23	<i>Pagellus erythrinus</i>	0.27	0.02	0.07
GTR	GSA-23	<i>Pagrus pagrus</i>	0.15	0.01	0.09
GTR	GSA-23	<i>Scorpaena scrofa</i>	0.08	0.02	0.24
GTR	GSA-23	<i>Squilla mantis</i>	0.96	0.02	0.02
GTR	GSA-23	<i>Parapenaeus longirostris</i>	0.63	0.23	0.37

Source: Greek DCF data of 2015

In addition, for Greece, the following data have been presented in the MEDAC proposal for joint recommendations on discards management plans for species defining the fisheries¹⁶:

Greek demersal fisheries are characterised by high diversity, both in terms of catch composition and the structure of the sector. The fisheries are typically multispecies, with a large variety of fishing gears being used to exploit the stocks. Although catches are composed of more than 100 commercial species, their bulk comprise 5 to 8 species, including hake, red mullets, and shrimps. Generally, fishing vessels exploiting the demersal stocks can be classified in two major fleet categories: (a) bottom trawlers and (b) artisanal or small-scale coastal vessels that mainly fish by means of various types of gillnets and longlines (Table 17).

Past studies have shown that discards vary among areas and seasons and the reason for discarding commercially important species is due to the size of the fish (undersized) and/or its condition (damaged individuals). Discards of the most important species are higher in the case of bottom trawlers but they are generally remaining at low levels (less than 5% of the total catch, in terms of weight, in most cases –Table 18).

The Greek bottom trawl fishery has multi-species characteristics and similarly to all Mediterranean demersal trawl fisheries, captures more than 100 commercial species. However, according to the records of the Greek Statistical Service, few of them such as red mullets, hake and shrimps compose the main bulk of landings.

Table 17: Greek annual catches and type of fishing activities in 2014

TARGET SPECIES			
	Hake	Red Mullet	Rose Shrimp
CATCHES			
Annual Total Landings* (tns)	2430	1915	2282
Landing Ports	1000+	1000+	236

¹⁶ See MEDAC Ref.: 190/2016 of June 8, 2016: http://en.med-ac.eu/files/documentazione_pareri_lettere/2016/06/190_medac_jr_lo_demersal_8june.pdf Accessed on 20/7/2016.

Type of fishing activities			
	Trawlers		
Number of fishing vessels	265	265	265
Landing Ports	236 (134**)	236 (127**)	236 (80**)
	Gillnets		
Number of fishing fleet	8032 (14806***)	8032 (14806***)	8032 (14806***)
Landing Ports	1000+	1000+	100
	Longlines		
Number of fishing fleet	8989 (14806***)		
Landing Ports	1000+		

Source: MEDAC Ref.: 190/2016 of June 8, 2016

** Landing ports where there were OTB landings reported through ERS during 2014-2015

*** Total number of vessels using passive gear

Table 18: Greek landings and discards 2014.

Gear	Species	Discards (t)	Landings (t)	% Discards
Bottom otter trawl	<i>Mullus barbatus</i>	16.259	972.800	1.64
Purse seine	<i>Mullus barbatus</i>	0	0.088	0
Set gillnet	<i>Mullus barbatus</i>	17.604	994.864	1.74
Trammel net*	<i>Mullus barbatus</i>	17.321	365.921	4.52
Bottom otter trawl	<i>Merluccius merluccius</i>	106.461	1,840.775	5.47
Set gillnet*	<i>Merluccius merluccius</i>	17.023	804.015	2.07
Set longlines*	<i>Merluccius merluccius</i>	0	235.964	0
Trammel net*	<i>Merluccius merluccius</i>	8.377	86.295	8.85
Bottom otter trawl	<i>Parapenaeus longirostris</i>	152.769	2,346.145	6.11

Source: MEDAC Ref.: 190/2016 of June 8, 2016

* estimated annual values based on 9 months data collection for Set gillnets, Trammel nets, Set longlines

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